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ENHANCING NURSE KNOWLEDGE REGARDING INCONTINENCE TO PREVENT
HOSPITAL ACQUIRED PRESSURE INJURIES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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ABSTRACT

Incontinence associated dermatitis (IAD) is a skin condition that occurs from prolonged exposure to urinary or fecal incontinence. Prevalence of IAD in the acute setting ranges from 18-95% and contributes to inflammation, pain, and increases risk of developing hospital acquired pressure injuries (HAPIs). There are deviations in evidence-based practice and management among healthcare professionals leading to misdiagnosis, improper IAD treatment, and HAPI development. This doctoral project examines the impact of enhancing nursing knowledge of IAD to reduce HAPIs using a pre- and post-implementation design. A convenience sample of 45 nurses, on a 34-bed Progressive Care Unit at an acute care facility in Southern California, participated in an IAD educational module to assess a change in nursing knowledge. The IAD education used two validated tools the Ghent Global IAD categorization tool (GLOBAID) and Knowledge Instrument on Incontinence-Associated Dermatitis for Clinicians (KNOW-IAD) to measure IAD etiology, classification, and management knowledge. Monthly and quarterly surveillance data of HAPI occurrence and incontinence incidence were collected. Participant scores resulted in an overall increase in nurse IAD knowledge while concurrently decreasing HAPIs with 62.5% of patients having incontinence ($p < .001$). Zero monthly HAPI's were noted four of the five months post-implementation, as well as on the next two consecutive prevalence studies. Expanding the education hospital wide and providing education annually will increase generalizability and streamline the implementation of IAD education. Nurse-driven IAD educational modules are effective in improving nursing knowledge of IAD and aid in reducing HAPI incidence.

Keywords: incontinence, incontinence associated dermatitis, hospital acquired pressure injuries, incontinence associated dermatitis education, evidence-based practice guidelines, risk factors

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Background

Incontinence is the involuntary and uncontrolled passage of urine or feces onto the skin. Incontinence is present in all healthcare settings ranging from critical care and medical-surgical units to long-term care facilities (Bliss et al., 2017). The exposure of incontinence moisture onto the skin predisposes it to break down swiftly and severely, leading to a condition known as incontinence associated dermatitis (IAD) (Coyer & Campbell, 2018). The onset of IAD can be rapid, cause massive skin destruction, and be challenging to manage (Fisher & Himan, 2020). The identification of IAD risk factors as well as early treatment can eliminate or slow the progression of IAD (Bliss et al., 2017; Campbell et al., 2019; Kayser et al., 2019).

Many studies have examined the risk factors for developing skin breakdown secondary to incontinence. Assessment of immobility, pressure injury pre-existence, Braden Scale score, low serum prealbumin and albumin levels, infection, poor skin condition, medications, impaired health status, cognitive impairment, tissue oxygenation disorder, obesity, inadequate skin care, incorrect use of absorbent products, repeated cleaning, liquid fecal incontinence, amount of fecal incontinence, and frequency of incontinence are all indicators that a patient is at risk for skin breakdown (Johansson et al., 2018; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021; Van Damme et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Delayed identification of risk factors for IAD can significantly impact the patient, nurse, and organization (Beekman et al., 2018; Kayser et al., 2021; Pather et al., 2021; Raepsaet et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021; Wei et al., 2019).

Scope of Incontinence

The risk factors of incontinence establish a strong case that almost every patient admitted into the acute care setting is vulnerable to developing IAD. Healthcare organizations need to provide measures that adequately identify and treat not only these risk factors but IAD itself.

Skin damage from IAD secondary to incontinence ranges from mild to severe and results in erythema, warmth, pain, itching, burning, and epidermal skin loss varying in depth from superficial to severe (Bliss et al., 2017; Kayser et al., 2019). Secondary complications of IAD disrupts the skin's natural barrier function and leads to a decrease in quality of life, prolonged hospital stays, skin infections, increased nurse workload, risk of hospital acquired pressure injury (HAPI) misdiagnosis, development and progression of pressure injuries, and a rise in medical costs (Beeckman, 2017; Beekman et al., 2018; Fisher & Himan, 2020; Gray & Giuliano, 2018; Koloms et al., 2022; Pather et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019).

The European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel, National Pressure Injury Advisory Panel and Pan Pacific Pressure Injury Alliance (EPUAP/NPIAP/PPPIA) provide organizations with recommendations, good practice statements, and implementation suggestions for pressure injury prevention and treatment (European Pressure Ulcer Advisory Panel, National Pressure Injury Advisory Panel and Pan Pacific Pressure Injury Alliance [EPUAP/NPIAP/PPPIA], 2019a, p.1). The EPUAP/NPIAP/PPPIA sets guidelines for hospitals to follow, suggests education strategies, and provides evidence-based treatments and recommendations for best practices and protocols. It is important to have specific guidelines for all nurses who are involved in patient care to refer to and follow, especially for the patients who are at risk or already have IAD or HAPIs. According to the EPUAP/NPIAP/PPPIA guidelines (2019b, pp.47-78; 2019c, pp. 84-89), moisture is a risk factor for developing a pressure injury, and preventative skin care through skin hygiene and continence management is essential to maintaining the skin's integrity. Not only is incontinence a risk factor for the development of HAPIs, but it also causes the pressure injuries to progress in severity. According to Kayser et al. (2021) incontinent patients showed higher rates of sacral pressure injury progression from stage 1 or 2 to stage 3 or 4 than patients who were continent.

Additionally, epidermal skin loss secondary to moisture is often misdiagnosed as a HAPI inflating the hospitals financial responsibility and diminishing its reputation leading consumers and stakeholders to assume that the hospital is providing substandard nursing care. (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018; Beeckman, 2017; Kayser et al., 2019, Kayser et al, 2021; Koloms et al., 2022; Pather et al., 2021; VanGilder, & Lachenbruch, 2018; Vickery et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019). Centers for Medicare and Medicaid Services (CMS) no longer reimburses for the treatment of HAPIs, as they are considered “reasonably preventable” and “never events” (CMS, 2021). Hospital acquired pressure injury cost is around \$10,708 per patient, with a single HAPI episode ranging anywhere from \$500 to \$70,000 and are a financial burden to the hospital (Padula & Delarmente, 2019). Nurses must understand the etiology, pathophysiology, appearance, and secondary complications of IAD to provide correct quality care to reduce the burden that pressure injuries bring to the patient, nurse, and organization.

Knowledge and Practice Gaps

To protect the patient, nurse, and organization from IAD and its secondary complications, it is important to assess the nurses’ education and knowledge on this topic. Even though many nurses manage incontinence daily, there is a general lack of knowledge and understanding regarding IAD and how to efficiently and effectively treat patients to prevent the development of HAPIs (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022a; Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022b; Şahin et al., 2019). Nurses’ frustration regarding guidance about incontinence treatment and management can lead to a decrease in job satisfaction, causing low-quality nursing care, and a decrease in patient positive outcomes (Baernholdt et al., 2020).

Problem Statement

The National Database for Nurse Quality Indicators (NDNQI), collects, analyzes, and sets benchmarks on patient quality and safety measures that are affected by nursing care to reflect the structure, process, and outcome of the care provided on a quarterly basis (National Database for Nursing Quality Indicators [NDNQI], n.d.; Press Ganey, 2022.). The data collected allows for hospitals to measure nurse quality indicators, one being HAPIs, regarding excellence in nursing care, gaps in care to improve, and decreasing or eliminating adverse events through reporting to drive change (Press Ganey, 2022). The data collected during the NDNQI can increase the hospital's financial penalties with an increase in cost, readmission rates, and length of stay, and affect the hospital's reputation for providing quality care. (EPUAP/NPIAP/PPPIA, 2019 c, pp. 11-13; Press Ganey, 2021).

During the NDNQI prevalence studies, at the study facility, the data collected exhibited a continual rise in the number of patients who had a moisture component increasing the risk for pressure injury development or deterioration due to excess moisture (Press Ganey, 2021). In 2020, the prevalence studies data yielded that 59% of patients surveyed had a moisture component, 2021 showing 57%, and the first three quarters of 2022 having 74% with zero HAPIs per the patient population being surveyed. The prevalence study data rate of zero was at the benchmark set by the facility and below the benchmark set by the NDNQI at around one.

Even though the NDNQI prevalence study HAPI data was at zero during the collection surveys, there was an increase in monthly HAPIs occurring on the PCU starting in January 2022. Of all the monthly HAPIs documented in 2020, 56% had a moisture component, 2021 60% had a moisture component, and the first nine months of 2022 had 75%. The steady rise in patients with a moisture component as well as the rise in monthly HAPIs, indicated that it was imperative to

educate the staff about incontinence and its secondary complications regarding its direct correlation with pressure injuries.

Purpose Statement

With a lack of targeted education regarding incontinence and its secondary complications the patient, nurse, and organization all suffer as patient quality outcomes can be directly linked to unmanaged incontinence care. The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing (DNP) evidence-based practice (EBP) project was to assess nurse knowledge regarding incontinence, fill in knowledge gaps with a standardized educational and management tool, and evaluate if knowledge was enhanced leading to a reduction of HAPIs. The aim of this project was to increase nurse knowledge regarding incontinence, provide an evidence-based treatment plan to decrease patient complications, and, in turn, reduce the development and deterioration of HAPIs.

Supporting Framework

The Iowa Model

Theoretical frameworks serve as a blueprint, guiding nurses through the investigation and implementation of an EBP change. Frameworks provide steps that a nurse can follow to identify an area of interest, investigate and institute a change plan, interpret findings, and adjust the plan as needed to enhance patient care and outcomes using current EBP (Titler et al., 2001). The Iowa Model is a frequently used theoretical framework that supports the transfer of knowledge from research into practice through a step-by-step methodical pathway to provide a sustainable change that enhances quality patient care (Appendix A). Permission to reproduce model is found in Appendix B (Titler et al., 1994; Titler et al., 2001).

The model, which relies on seven steps and three decision points, was initially created by Marita G. Titler and seven colleagues at the University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics in 1994.

Titler et al. (1994) outlined how to identify a clinical problem, research EBP on implementing a positive change, tailor, pilot a trial, and evaluate results to find a solution to enhance patient care outcomes and create sustainable change (Titler et al., 1994). The team revised the model in 2017 to adapt to the changing infrastructure of the healthcare system (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). The Iowa Model is an ideal framework for this DNP project as it focuses on clear and concise steps to implement an EBP initiative to create a positive and sustainable change for patients (Chiwaula et al., 2021).

Steps and Application of Iowa Model to Current Project

According to the Iowa Model Collaborative (2017), clinicians who use the Iowa Model ask questions and seek systematic evidence-based steps to promote excellence in healthcare that nurses can use to create and sustain real change. The first and second steps of the Iowa Model are to identify a problem resulting from a triggering event that needs to be corrected and develop the project's purpose statement (Titler et al., 2001). For this DNP project, the triggering event was the increase in monthly HAPIs in the Progressive Care Unit (PCU) and a rise in patients who had an identified moisture component on the prevalence study collection sheets. A root cause analysis was performed, which indicated that most of the monthly HAPI events had a moisture component. The facility does have a pressure injury prevention protocol (PIP) Bundle that addresses incontinence, as well as an incontinence protocol, but the nurses need further education on specifics regarding incontinence and its link to HAPIs. Nurses need to understand incontinence, its secondary complications, and management actions to treat incontinence moisture to prevent skin breakdown.

The next step in the Iowa Model is to establish the purpose of the evidence-based change project. The purpose of this DNP project was to assess nurse knowledge regarding incontinence,

fill in knowledge gaps with a standardized educational and management tool, and evaluate if knowledge was enhanced leading to a reduction of HAPIs. The goal of this project was to develop an evidence-based standardized educational module that will address incontinence recognition, treatment, and management to decrease HAPI development while at the same time improving patient health outcomes and nursing care on an adult inpatient unit in a hospital in Southern California.

After defining the purpose statement, the following step is the first of three decision points, which provide a feedback loop, direction, fine-tuning of the problem, leadership support, identification of resources needed, available data, and verification that the problem is a priority for the organization (Iowa Model Collaborative, 2017). In this case, the project correlates with the organization's focus on zero HAPI development, providing quality evidence-based care, implementing best practices for the patient and medical group, and increasing nurse autonomy and education.

After confirming that an incontinence education module is important for patient care, nurse advancement, and reducing HAPIs, the Iowa Model guides the user to form a multidisciplinary team to solve the practice problem. The primary objective of this step is to identify and recruit stakeholders who can brainstorm and use their knowledge and expertise to address the problem and form a cohesive team. The primary goal of the team is to create a timeframe and establish team expectations for the project (Titler et al., 2001). The team is accountable for supporting the implementation of the project and the team lead in establishing an EBP change. The team is responsible for encouraging nursing staff participation, providing time flexibility in learning the EBP activity, and collecting feedback to bring back to the group regarding the implementation of the change project (Lacerenza et al., 2018). For this project, the

interdisciplinary team included the project-lead, fellow certified wound, ostomy, and continence nurse (CWOCN), Executive Director of Critical Care, Executive Director of Acute Care Nursing, and the PCU Director and Manager.

The fourth step of the Iowa Model involves gathering and analyzing literature related to the proposed change. The literature was searched through multiple databases looking into the problem with specifics regarding incontinence and prevalence, HAPIs, IAD, incontinence treatment, nurse knowledge, satisfaction, and confidence in treating incontinence and IAD. Articles were peer-reviewed, no more than five years old, qualitative and quantitative studies including quasi-experimental, randomized control trials, experimental, meta-analysis, and systematic reviews. An extensive literature search found sufficient evidence to support the change and allowed the team to continue to step five of the Iowa model.

The fifth step includes creating and designing the pilot project to address the issue described in steps one and two and entails the following: (a) developing outcomes to be achieved; (b) analyzing resources, limitations, and endorsement; (c) elaborating a specific protocol; (d) creating an assessment plan; (e) collecting baseline data; (f) creating an implementation proposal; (g) recruiting clinicians and establishing supplies; (h) encouraging acceptance; and (i) aggregating and disseminating post-pilot data (Titler et al., 2001). The target population for this project was PCU staff nurses, monthly HAPI incidence, and the data collected from the NDNQI prevalence study. A nurse education program was developed to teach all bedside nurses on this unit about incontinence, its secondary complications, identification, and EBP management of incontinence. In preparing for the pilot, the project-lead carefully analyzed all resources and limitations, including educational brochure printouts and nurse education time. The Executive Director of Acute Care Nursing granted approval of all required material and time

to support this project which directly aligned with the organization's goal to enhance nurse knowledge regarding incontinence and decrease HAPI development.

Next is the third and last decision point at which the project team needs to decide if the piloted practice change is appropriate for organizational adoption. The analysis of the statistical data produced by the pilot project allows for exploring any improvements, limitations, constraints, successes, and resources needed to turn the pilot into practice (Titler et al., 2001). The sixth and seventh steps of the Iowa Model revolve around this decision point. The sixth step analyzes the results of the pilot change if the change is feasible and if results improved outcomes. The critical outcome of this step, after support from stakeholders, is the integration and hardwiring of the change into the system to sustain quality care improvements effectively.

The seventh and last step of the Iowa Model is disseminating the pilot project results to enhance EBP change with a broader audience. There must be a growth in EBP to encourage and facilitate new research and understanding of improving patient care (Titler et al., 2001). The project-lead disseminated the results to the Executive Director of Critical Care and the Executive Director of Acute Care Nursing. The project will continue the PCU If and when deemed appropriate will be adopted on a larger scale, these stakeholders will discuss the change with all adult medicine Directors to implement the change facility wide. Once the change is sustained and adopted into all adult medicine units at the project's facility, the researcher can share the findings with other facilities, community organizations, and local, regional, and national conferences.

The seven steps of the Iowa Model allow for a guided process in which a problem can be identified, addressed, and changed through systematic steps supported by EBP. The project-lead used the Iowa Model to guide the implementation of an incontinence education module that was

created, piloted, and evaluated to execute a progressive change in this facility and on a larger scale. The outcome of this project is to positively enhance nurses' ability to provide safe and quality care by increasing IAD knowledge in recognizing, treating, and managing incontinence to decrease HAPIs.

Review of Literature

Overview

The purpose of this DNP EBP project was to create, implement, and evaluate the effectiveness of an incontinence education module to increase nurse knowledge regarding incontinence to decrease HAPIs. The importance of providing a detailed literature review and table of evidence regarding incontinence as it affects the patient, nurse, and organization is foundational when completing the steps of the Iowa Model to promote excellence in care (Appendix C).

Search Strategy Methods

The literature review focused on understanding incontinence, secondary complications, IAD educational tools, and nurse knowledge to develop and implement an effective nursing education program to increase knowledge and decrease HAPIs. The California State University, Fullerton Pollack Library, manual searches through reputable peer-reviewed journals, and reference lists were utilized to retrieve relevant articles. Electronic databases used in the literature review were PubMed, Cumulative Index to Nursing and Allied Health Literature/EBSCO, Science Direct, and OneSearch. Search strategies included using Boolean operations with the term incontinence associated dermatitis and “development,” “barriers,” “prevalence,” “HAPI,” “risk factors,” “length of stay,” “readmission,” “cost,” and “knowledge.” MeSH- terms were also used to explore additional articles on this topic. Standard limiters used to narrow the search and establish relevant, up to date information included only peer-reviewed articles in or translated into English published between 2017 and 2023 and in nursing, healthcare, and professional journals.

Review of Literature Search Results

The focus of the literature review encompassed several main topics, including complications secondary to incontinence, barriers to incontinence management, lack of incontinence knowledge, and consequences of lack of knowledge. The following review of literature discusses incontinence and provides a strong foundation for the importance of initiating an educational program focused on incontinence to reduce HAPI development. The online search yielded 240 articles, but upon further analysis, only 35 were included in the literature review, with others eliminated due to duplicates, lack of relevance to the project, more updated research, or being a quality improvement project (Appendix C). The main topics surrounding incontinence and nurse knowledge revolved around how lack of IAD knowledge leads to mismanaged incontinence, increases patient risk for skin erosion, misdiagnosis, and development of HAPIs, and other secondary complications.

Complications Secondary to Incontinence

The development of IAD secondary to incontinence occurs when there is damage to the skin's integrity after being exposed to urine and feces (Gray et al., 2022; Johansen et al., 2018; Kayser et al., 2021). The clinical presentation of IAD appears as inflammation and swelling of the skin with mild to severe erythema with or without open erosions (Coyer et al., 2020). The hostile environment of untreated IAD leaves the skin over-hydrated, inflamed, and tender (Gray & Giuliano, 2018; Gray et al., 2022). Incontinence moisture can damage the skin in as short as ten to 15 minutes, with the average length of time for occurrence being around four days (Banharak et al., 2021; Beeckman, 2017; Stehlow et al., 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018).

Incontinence Associated Dermatitis

The process of skin damage secondary to incontinence is a complex process stemming from two main issues that alter the skin barrier: over-hydration of the skin and changes in skin pH. (Bliss et al., 2017; Gates et al., 2019; Grey et al., 2022; Johansen et al., 2018; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021). Incontinence from urine creates a cyclical situation where the skin becomes damaged from over-hydration causing the outer layer of skin, or the stratum corneum, to swell (Coyer & Campbell, 2018; Beeckman, 2017; Fisher & Himan, 2020; Gray et al., 2022; Johansen et al., 2018; Voegeli & Hillery, 2021). The protective ability of the skin's natural pH and microclimate are also affected due to the urea and ammonia in the urine and become more permeable to bacteria that will infiltrate the skin, causing inflammation, irritation, cutaneous infections, and deterioration of the skin layers (Beeckman, 2017; Coyer & Campbell, 2018; Johansen et al., 2018). Excess moisture and over-hydration of the skin secondary to extra urine exposure causes the skin to be more susceptible to pressure, friction damage, shear forces, and mechanical trauma (Fisher & Himan, 2020; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021; Voegeli & Hillery, 2021).

Urinary incontinence alone is not the only contributor to IAD. Fecal incontinence has a synergistic effect when combined with urine as it changes the skin's pH, causing the risk and severity of IAD to increase significantly (Banharak et al., 2021; Beeckman, 2017; Coyer & Campbell, 2018; Coyer et al., 2020; Voegeli & Hillery, 2021). Fecal bacteria, urease, digestive enzymes, lipase, and protease, become activated in an alkaline environment due to the transformation of urea into ammonia and will begin to break down the proteins and fat in the stratum corneum, degrading and damaging the skin (Coyer & Campbell, 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018; Voegeli & Hillery, 2021). Many studies have also inferred that liquid stool, which

contains bile salts, enzymes, and pancreatic lipase, further increases the risk of developing IAD (Beeson et al., 2017; Campbell et al., 2019; Ferreria et al., 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Fecal consistency, duration of contact, volume, and frequency increase the likelihood of IAD development through changes in the microclimate of the skin enhancing the risk of skin trauma secondary to pressure, friction, and shear forces (Campbell et al., 2019; Francis et al., 2017; Hödl & Eglseer, 2020; Johansen et al., 2018; Kayser et al., 2019; Van Damme et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019).

Incontinence generally affects the elderly population as the skin is more vulnerable to exterior irritants and trauma secondary to atrophy, an increase in fragility, and a decrease in flexibility, however IAD can occur across all age groups (Coyer et al., 2017; Strehlow et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018). Multiple sources suggest that IAD prevalence in the acute care setting ranges from 18% to 50% to 15% to 95% (Arnold-Long & Johnson, 2019; Bliss et al., 2017; Campbell et al., 2019; Coyer et al., 2017; Pather et al., 2021). Multiple factors cause the wide range of IAD occurrences in the hospital with the most common being the underreporting of IAD due to a lack of knowledge of its clinical presentation or from misclassifying the skin loss as a pressure injury (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022a; Beeckman, 2017; Fisher & Himan, 2020; Gray et al., 2022).

Patient Impact Secondary to Incontinence

A patient with IAD will experience intense burning and stinging pain that causes episodes of excruciating discomfort. Even sedated patients show signs of distress when the inflamed skin is cleaned (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018; Fisher & Himan, 2020). Patients with IAD will also suffer from longer healing rates, possible infection, immobility, susceptibility to pressure injury development and progression, increased morbidity, extended hospitalizations,

higher readmission rates, and cost increase contributing to a lowered quality of life (Arnold-Long et al., 2018; Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018a; Beekman et al., 2018; Bliss et al., 2017; Coyer & Campbell, 2018; Fisher & Himan, 2020; Gray & Giuliano, 2018; Kayser et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018). An incontinent patient is more likely to develop a HAPI, ranging from partial to full thickness, when compared to a continent patient (Banbarak et al., 2021; Kayser et al., 2021; Gray & Giuliano, 2018). Healthcare professionals must be educated on properly identifying and treating IAD to protect the patient from developing the secondary consequences of incontinence.

Nurse Impact Secondary to Incontinence

The impact IAD has on the bedside nurse can prove to be daunting as there is an increase in nursing workload when a patient has IAD (del Cotillo-Fuente et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019). The management of IAD can be labor-intensive, and a daily challenge for healthcare providers contributing to nurse-burnout (Johansson et al., 2018; Raepsaet et al., 2021; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021). Incontinence associated dermatitis onset and progression can be rapid, and without a method of detecting and treating it, can start a vicious cycle of deteriorating skin (Campbell et al., 2019; Fisher & Himan, 2020). Once a patient develops IAD, nursing resources are taxed causing a decrease in job satisfaction, nurse-sensitive indicators, and quality care (Kayser et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019). Enhancing nurse knowledge and treatment regarding incontinence and its secondary complications will positively impact patients physically and mentally by decreasing secondary complications of incontinence.

Organizational Impact Secondary to Incontinence

Incontinence associated dermatitis directly impacts the healthcare organization monetarily due to increased medical costs and hospital stays treating the secondary

complications that arise from IAD (Beekman et al., 2018; Francis et al., 2017; Ferreria et al., 2018; Fisher & Himan, 2020; Johansen et al., 2018; Kayser et al., 2019; Raepsaet et al., 2021; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019). Pressure injury development during a hospital stay is considered a poor indicator of quality of care by multiple agencies including the California Department of Health (CDPH), CMS, NDNQI, and The Joint Commission (TJC) (California Department of Public Health [CDPH], 2017; Centers for Medicare & Medicaid Services [CMS], 2021; The Joint Commission [TJC], 2022; National Database for Nursing Quality Indicators [NDNQI], 2010; Schmitt et al., 2017). Hospitals are required to report progressed HAPIs to the CDPH as they are considered an adverse event in which further investigation of patient care is analyzed with the organization facing penalties (CDPH, 2017).

Many hospitals strive to be accredited by the TJC, who strives to improve the healthcare provided to patients by evaluating if the settings quality and safety standards are up to the accreditation standard (TJC, 2023). Starting in 2022, TJC revised its standards and performance expectations to reflect HAPIs current guidelines and best practices that were set by the EPUAP/NPIAP/PPPIA (TJC, 2021).

In addition to HAPIs playing a part in being accredited by TJC, they also play a part in a facility striving for Magnet® status, which is the highest credential for nursing facilities who provide nursing excellence to the highest standard of care set by the American Nurses Credentialing Center. (American Nurses Credentialing Center [ANCC], n.d.). One of the criteria of a Magnet® designation requires the hospital to collect nurse quality indicators, one being HAPIs, at the benchmark and unit level to compare data to other organizations (ANCC, n.d.). Hospital acquired pressure injuries secondary to IAD mismanagement will increase the data

collected during the NDNQI, misrepresenting the population and the nursing care hindering the hospital's ability to become a Magnet® facility (Press Ganey, 2021).

As forementioned, the NDNQI collects, analyzes, and sets benchmarks on patient quality and safety measures that are affected by nursing care to reflect the structure, process and outcome of the care provided on a quarterly basis (NDNQI, n.d.; Press Ganey, 2022.). The data collected allows for hospitals to measure nurse indicators regarding quality nursing care, gaps in care to improve, and decreasing or eliminating adverse events through reporting to drive change (Press Ganey, 2022). The data collected during the NDNQI can increase the hospital's financial penalties with an increase in cost, readmission rates, and length of stay and affect the hospital's reputation for providing quality care. (EPUAP/NPIAP/PPPIA, 2019 c, pp. 11-13; Press Ganey, 2021).

Barriers to Incontinence Management

Skin assessment, treatment, and management are essential aspects of nursing care. Nurses are trained on pressure injury treatment but are not well versed in research-based incontinence and IAD treatment (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018a; Zhang et al., 2021). Patients admitted to the acute care setting often have a diminished physiological, cognitive, and sensory reactions to skin irritation caused by incontinence moisture. Consequently, it is the care providers' responsibility to assess and manage incontinent issues promptly and accurately (Van Damme et al., 2018). Lack of knowledge regarding IAD result in a delay or misuse of treatment, misdiagnosis of IAD, and variation in practice, which can lead to patient harm, a decrease in professional care, and an increase in organizational costs and hospital stays (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022a; Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022b; Beekman et al., 2018; Gray et al., 2022; Raepsaet et al., 2021; Şahin et al., 2019; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019).

Lack of Knowledge and Education Regarding Incontinence

Even though there is a growing interest surrounding incontinence, studies suggest there is still a lack of nurse understanding regarding IAD etiology, identification, assessment, prevention, management, treatment and secondary complications leading to the progression of skin breakdown, patient harm, hospitalization cost, and nurse workload (Baernholdt et al., 2020; Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018a; Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022a ;Beekman et al., 2018; Coyer et al., 2017; del Cotillo-Fuente et al., 2021; Qiang et al., 2020; Şahin et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021; Ostaszkievicz et al., 2020; Van den Bussche et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2018; Wei et al., 2019; Zhang et al., 2021). Assessing and providing current evidence-based, unified, comprehensive educational program regarding IAD will allow for less variability in care and cohesion use of EBP standards to enhancing patient care (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022a; Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022b; Şahin et al., 2019; Strehlow et al., 2018; Ostaszkievicz et al., 2020).

While the literature does support that education on incontinence practices improves nurse knowledge regarding incontinence, the most effective forms of education regarding IAD, e.g., web, classroom, or peer to peer-based education etc., to assure practice change and enhanced patient outcomes are unknown (Ostaszkievicz et al., 2020). There also appears to be a gap in the literature regarding the long-term effect of incontinence education and nurse knowledge with the development of HAPIs and patient outcomes. This DNP project assesses nurse knowledge pre- and post-education on incontinence and investigates if this knowledge over time decreases the development of HAPIs, aiding in filling the gap of literature available regarding this topic.

Nurse Education to Enhance Incontinence and Pressure Injury Prevention

Education is a key component to providing patients with current evidence-based care. Evidence suggests that educating nurses regarding incontinence and pressure injury development improves appropriate treatment and pressure injury prevention (Aquino et al., 2019; Qiang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). Maintaining the integrity of a patient's skin is a foundational expectation of the bedside nurse. Providing education regarding pressure injury prevention, including moisture management, raises awareness, changes cultural norms, addresses behaviors that are not evidence-based, and influences healthcare professionals to provide current and evidence-based care (Aquino et al., 2019; Smith et al., 2018). The key to a successful evidence-based education program regarding incontinence and pressure injuries includes education done by experts in the field, posters, handouts, online training, and interactive activities (Aydin et al., 2019; Coyer et al., 2017; de Cortillo-Fuente et al., 2021; Fisher & Himan, 2020). It is important to uncover gaps in knowledge when creating an educational module to fine tune the information provided to fill in all disparities on the topic.

Conclusion

Current research confirms the prevalence, cause, and treatment of incontinence and has identified that nurses lack evidence-based knowledge regarding incontinence and its role in pressure injury development (Aydin et al., 2019; Gray & Giuliano, 2018; Şahin et al., 2019). Based on this literature review, incontinence education must be standardized to enhance nurse knowledge and patient care. Nurses must be given education to grow their foundational knowledge of incontinence to then be able to provide standardized care to properly and comprehensively, treat IAD and decrease the risk for HAPI development.

Methods

The purpose of this DNP EBP project was to assess, develop, implement, and evaluate an evidence-based nurse educational module related to incontinence and its secondary complications. The goal of this project was to evaluate a change in knowledge and practice as it relates to identifying and treating incontinence using EBP. The project-lead also aimed to assess if the educational module resulted in decreasing the number of monthly HAPIs developing secondary to incontinence as well as maintaining zero HAPIs reported during the NDNQI quarterly prevalence study.

Design

The DNP project used a pre- and post-implementation design. A convenience sample of nurses from the PCU who met the inclusion criteria completed a pre-test assessing incontinence knowledge using two validated tools, the Ghent Global IAD Categorization tool (GLOBAID) and Knowledge Instrument on Incontinence-Associated Dermatitis for Clinicians (KNOW-IAD). The nurses received formal education on incontinence, secondary complications, identification, and management through a 15-minute verbal educational module and brochure. Each nurse then took the post-test within their 12-hour shift to evaluate their knowledge level after listening to and participating in the module. The monthly HAPI report and the publicly available NDNQI prevalence study data was then analyzed to see if the knowledge received through the education model aided in decreasing HAPIs with a moisture component.

Setting

The setting for this project was on the PCU of a 317-bed acute care Magnet[®] facility in Southern, California. The facility includes emergency, surgical, intensive care, step down, telemetry, medical-surgical, labor & delivery, neonatal intensive, and postpartum units. The

facility also specializes in bariatric wellness, a spine institute, cancer services, cardiovascular excellence, stroke and neuroscience, diabetes and nutritional services, orthopedics, rehabilitation, transitional care, and home care. The PCU specializes in cardiac monitoring with a 3:1 nurse to patient ratio with 34 beds.

Sample

The PCU unit was comprised of 71 registered nurses (RNs). The inclusion criteria for this project included all RNs that work directly with patients on either shift (0700-1930 or 1900-0730), administrative nurses in the PCU, and charge nurses. Exclusion criteria comprised any non-RNs, including certified nursing assistants or licensed vocation nurses, and any non-bedside RNs. All nurses working in the PCU were recruited with the goal of enrolling 50 of the 71 RNs.

Stakeholders

Multiple stakeholders were identified as key players in the facilitation and implementation of this DNP project. At the administrative level, there was engagement and interest in this project. These stakeholders supported assessing nurse understanding regarding patient care issues to fill knowledge gaps to improve quality care. In addition, these stakeholders supported this project since the number of patients with incontinence were rising and is a risk factor for the development of HAPIs, which negatively affects the organization fiscally and hinders the organization's reputation for providing quality care. Administrative stakeholders included the Executive Director of Critical Care, Executive Director of Acute Care Nursing, and the PCU Director and Manager. These stakeholders were responsible for approving the project, empowering the project-lead to implement an EBP project, and encouraging the staff to complete the project with fidelity and enthusiasm (Smith et al., 2018). A letter of support was provided to the project-lead from these administrative stakeholders (Appendix D).

There were also stakeholders at the team and committee level who aided in adjusting the project to best fit the needs of the patients, staff, and organization which was comprised of the project-lead, fellow CWOCN, and the skin champions on the PCU. The team ensured that the project was evidence-based, in alignment with best practices according to the NPIAP and NDNQI, and per the hospital's goals and commitment to patient care. Team members also reviewed and monitored the educational module to ensure that proper practices were taking place after the educational module implementation. Lastly, the team aided in evaluating any long-term change by collecting HAPI data monthly and quarterly for the NDNQI prevalence study. The project-lead was responsible for analyzing and evaluating the data from the project to determine if the incontinence educational module was effective in increasing nurse knowledge and treatment of incontinence as well as reducing HAPIs. At the committee level, the Unit-Based Council, SkinSational Team, and Nursing Research Council participated in the project. These committees were instituted and consulted to give insightful information, review policies, and ensure institutional review board (IRB) application was done correctly. These stakeholders provided a strong foundation that ensured that the DNP project was implemented efficiently.

The department-level stakeholders aided in the recruitment and implementation of the project. These stakeholders included multiple charge nurses on both day and night shifts and nurse leads dedicated to the PCU. These individuals kept the project on track, encouraged participation, directed staff nurses to resources, and held staff accountable to the education module. Stakeholders in this group also reported back to the project-lead if there were any questions or concerns regarding the implementation of the educational module.

Ethical Considerations

The IRB was consulted for the facility where the project was implemented and from California State University, Fullerton. Participation in this project was voluntary and associated with no more than minimal risk to participants (Appendix E). A cover letter with a description of the project and an informed consent to participate in the study was given to staff. Participants chose a unique individual three-digit participation identification code by combining their birth month, last initial of mother's maiden name, and last digit of birth year to secure anonymity. Participation was voluntary and assumed via the signed consent and the completion of the survey. All data was kept confidential and stored on a password-protected computer or in a locked cabinet in the wound care office.

Data Collection

Data collection included a demographic survey, responses to the pre- and post-test, monthly HAPI incidence and quarterly NDNQI HAPI and moisture prevalence. Data was collected at several time periods: before presenting the educational module, after the completion of the educational module, retrospective monthly HAPI incidence from the last three years, monthly HAPI incidence five months following the education module, retrospective NDNQI HAPI and moisture prevalence from the last three years, and NDNQI HAPI and moisture prevalence for two quarters after the educational module. The informed consent, demographic data, pre- and post-test were created using paper printouts. The demographic information that was collected from the nursing staff participating included current work area/unit name, work shift, current position, role, length of time in the current role, position, or profession, and length of time working in the current work area/unit, educational level, age, and gender.

Ghent Global IAD Categorization Tool

The GLOBAID allows for a universal IAD classification system. The tool is important as it provides a standard description with photos of different categories of IAD lesions, and respondents are rated based on whether they identified the correct category. The tool divides IAD into two categories depending on the severity: Category 1 appears as persistent redness and category 2 presents with skin loss. Each category is further subdivided into two categories based on infection: A being without signs of infection and B with signs of infection. Therefore, the tool provides four categories for IAD: Category 1A persistent redness without clinical signs of infection, category 1B persistent redness with clinical signs of infection, category 2A skin loss without clinical signs of infection, and category 2B skin loss with clinical signs of infection. There are additional clinical characteristics listed on the tool for further description of each category (Beeckman et al., 2018).

The tool was tested for inter- and intra-rater reliability with content and face validity and sensitivity and specificity estimates using a three-round Delphi procedure with a sample of 823 health professionals in 30 countries (Beeckman et al., 2018). The results of the study by Beeckman et al. (2018) showed an 86% [95% CI 0.86-0.87] agreement in the ability to differentiate between Category 1 and Category 2, a 90% sensitivity, and an 84% specificity. The Fleiss and Cohen's Kappa for differentiating between Category 1 and Category 2 used a 95% confidence interval and showed substantial agreement with an overall Fleiss and Cohen's Kappa showing moderate to substantial agreement (Beeckman et al., 2018). Permission to reproduce the tool was obtained, and a copy is included in Appendix F.

Knowledge Instrument on Incontinence-Associated Dermatitis for Clinicians

The KNOW-IAD is an 18-item validated instrument developed to analyze nurses' knowledge of IAD in relation to three separate knowledge categories: etiology and risk, classification and diagnosis, and prevention and management. The tool takes five to ten minutes to complete. The responses for this tool are true, false, and don't know, with one point being awarded to each correct answer with all items being weighted equally. Incorrect, missing, or "don't know" responses are all given a zero. The range of possible scores from each category is: etiology and risk domain zero to seven points, classification, and diagnosis domain zero to five points, and prevention and management domain zero to six points. The sum of each category is added for a total score with a maximum score of 18 and a satisfactory score of 70%, which equates to correctly responding on 13 questions (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2022a; Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2022b).

The instrument displayed good validity and reliability properties with a three-phase development and testing approach showing high scale content validity ratios and indices scores on relevance and clarity when analyzed by a 15-participant panel. The composite reliability of this tool was good for the etiology/risk section and prevention/management section while being adequate for the classification/diagnosis section when 204 participants received the instrument (Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2022a; Bakarath-Johnson et al., 2022b). Permission to reproduce the instrument was obtained and can be found in Appendix G.

Monthly Data and National Database for Nurse Quality Indicators

The monthly HAPI data was retrieved from the HAPI trending tool that compiles all imperative data linked to a pressure injury and is utilized by the CWOCN, unit Managers and Directors, and the quality department. The prevalence study is a point in time calculation that

looks at the number of HAPIs divided by the total number of patients in the unit being studied. The purpose of the NDNQI prevalence study is to determine the rate of HAPI occurrence and explore the relationship between nursing care, interventions used, and pressure injury development by aggregating the data into groups (Press Ganey, 2021).

The prevalence study is conducted four times per year by trained nurses using the NDNQI standardized tool. The NDNQI data is reported to Press Ganey and then is compared to other organizations unit-based specific quality indicators. The scores on the NDNQI allow for unit transparency and unit-specific action plans to be created to improve areas that do not meet the benchmarks. The reliability of the standardized tool has been examined by a triangulation approach that included direct observation and web-based testing and with an overall k coefficient for pressure injury identification, staging, and origin of moderate to near-perfect reliability (Bergquist-Beringer, 2011; Press Ganey, 2021).

Procedures

After the approval of all stakeholders and the IRB from the facility and California State University, Fullerton, the PCU staff was informed verbally during rounding, start of shift huddle, and mid-shift huddle about the upcoming project with its purpose and given an invitation to participate. The staff was prepared in advance of the upcoming project and was instructed to contact the wound department for any additional questions due to being the first doctoral project on this unit.

Pre-Implementation Data Collection

Baseline monthly HAPI incidence, quarterly NDNQI prevalence study HAPI data and moisture management information was collected prior to beginning the project from quarter one 2020 through quarter three 2022. For three weeks prior to the IAD education, nurses who agreed

to participate in the project were given an informed consent, a demographic survey, and the pre-test, including the GLOBAID and KNOW-IAD via a paper handout in person to collect baseline data and gaps in knowledge on incontinence (Appendix H; Appendix I; Appendix J). Nurses were instructed to complete the informed consent, demographic survey, and pre-test within their 12-hour shift. The project-lead would collect the forms during the day and the charge nurse would collect the forms during the night shift in which the project-lead or CWOCN would collect in the morning. All completed forms were placed in an envelope, secured in the CWOCN office, and stored in a locked cabinet. For the next three weeks all nurses working, including those who did not want to participate, were given the IAD education but only those who completed the informed consent completed the post-test (Appendix J).

Educational Intervention

The educational module began once all pre-test data was collected, and a participant sample size of at least 30 was achieved. Educational events took place for three weeks during start of shift or mid-shift huddles alternating between day and night shifts. There were no incentives provided to the staff. The IAD education module and brochure, which was created by the project-lead, had content from the GLOBAID and KNOW-IAD. A brochure was given to staff with a five to seven minute oral presentation going over all written material, followed by five minutes for questions (Appendix K). The presentation included an incontinence overview, secondary complications of incontinence, the different categories of IAD with management and treatment expectations for incontinence. A printout of the treatment guideline protocol for incontinence and pressure injuries, which included information from the educational module, was posted at each nursing station with instructions and pictures of individual products to aid in nurse standardization of incontinence treatment.

Post-Implementation Data Collection

After the IAD education and questions, the nurses were given the option to complete the post-test immediately which took another five to seven minutes or complete the post-test by the end of their 12-hour shift. The post-test was the same printed pre-test comprised of both the GLOBAID and KNOW-IAD. The project-lead would collect the forms during the day and the charge nurse would collect the forms during the night shift in which the project-lead or CWOCN would collect in the morning. All completed forms were placed in an envelope, secured in the CWOCN office, and stored in a locked cabinet. After the educational module and post-tests, the monthly HAPI incidence was collected from October 2022 through February 2023 and the NDNQI HAPI prevalence and moisture management data was collected from quarter four 2022 and quarter one 2023.

Timeline of Project

April 2022: Student onboarding process at facility

May 2022: Defense proposal

June 2022: Defend to Nursing Research Council

July 2022: Facility IRB approval

August 2022: School IRB approval

September & October 2022: Nurse recruitment, implementation of the project, data collection

November 2022-February 2023: Data collection, data analysis, results, and discussion

Data Analysis

The project-lead utilized Intellectus Statistics TM and QI Macros[®] to analyze changes in nurse knowledge related to incontinence and changes in HAPI occurrence. Intellectus Statistics TM was used for frequency distribution of the demographic and to conduct the statistical analyses

of nurse knowledge data. The Chi-square test was used to compare the observed results of the pre-and post-tests with the expected results to determine if there was a statistically significant difference between IAD education and enhanced nurse knowledge both overall and on each individual question. QI Macros® was used to review if the process change, IAD education, affected the HAPI incidence and prevalence over time. The program was utilized to convert the monthly HAPI incidence and NDNQI prevalence study data from quarter one 2020 through quarter one 2023 into control charts to analyze if the IAD education started a process change to decrease the occurrence of HAPIs on the PCU.

Evaluation Plan

The goal of this project was to not only increase nurse knowledge regarding incontinence, its secondary complications, and treatment but also decrease HAPI incidence and prevalence in the PCU. The long-term evaluation plan for enhancing nurse knowledge regarding incontinence to prevent HAPIs includes continual reinforcement of the education module by weekly rounding, follow-up education, evaluation of incontinence management, and answering any additional questions or educational needs in the PCU. Once project success is established, and to ensure sustainability, the educational material will also be presented to adult patient units, new hire, and nurse graduate orientation, and in staff meetings to properly standardize the knowledge and treatment for IAD. The monthly HAPI incidence will also be continually added to the control chart for the rest of 2023 to analyze if there is a process change seen by a special cause variation related to the IAD education implementation. Lastly, the NDNQI HAPI prevalence and moisture management data will be collected and compared with benchmark data to evaluate if the IAD education aids in sustaining a low HAPI prevalence with incontinent patients.

Conclusion

To provide best-practice care focused on nurse sensitive indicators, it is important for organizations to recognize areas where there can be improvement in patient outcomes. Structuring focused time, resources, and education to fill in knowledge and practice gaps allows for an organization to produce better and safer care. As HAPIs and incontinence rates rose on the PCU the nurse and organization were challenged to assess, research, create, fill, and analyze if IAD education would enhance knowledge and decrease HAPIs. Nurses need to be aware of incontinence and the expectations on how to recognize, treat and manage this painful condition to decrease the progression of skin complications and give timely and adequate care regarding incontinence. The goal of this DNP project was implementation of an evidence-based IAD educational module to enhance nurse knowledge generating a change in the current process to decrease HAPI misdiagnosis, development, or deterioration. The development and implementation of an evidence-based nurse educational module is the first step in raising awareness and giving a foundation for the nurses to grow their confidence and ability to treat incontinence and decrease HAPIs.

Results

The goal of this DNP EBP project aimed to increase nurses' knowledge regarding incontinence to prevent the misdiagnosis, development, and progression of pressure injuries through the analysis of the monthly HAPI incidence and NDNQI pressure injury prevalence study. All staff who participated completed two validated tools that assessed their prior knowledge regarding IAD. After completion of the pre-test, staff received the IAD education module during shift huddles as all nurses are together with fewer patient care interruptions to allow for a timely presentation of materials. After the education, during their 12-hour shift the nurses completed the same post-test to analyze if there was an increase in knowledge. The aggregate of all correct responses from the pre- and post-test were collected to look at the distribution of observed over expected responses. Using Intellectus Statistics™, bivariate associations were tested using Chi-square X^2 with a 95% confidence interval and a p -value $< .05$, to assess if a relationship existed between the education IAD module and the frequency of correct nurse responses to determine if there was a difference in the pre- and post-test results. The monthly HAPI incidence and NDNQI prevalence study data were then collected and analyzed with control charts using QI Macros® to assess if the nurses new IAD knowledge caused a special cause variation resulting in the reduction HAPIs on the PCU.

Demographic Characteristics

Intellectus Statistics™ was used to create descriptive statistics on the demographic variables (Appendix L). There were 45 nurse participants, with the majority of nurses (44.44%) being in the 30-35 years old range. The AM shift included 62.22% of the participants, with the PM shift accounting for 37.78%. The gender of the participants was 13.33% male and 86.67% female. Of the nurses that participated, 95.56% worked on the pilot unit and had worked on this

unit for zero to two years (37.78%), three to five years (22.22%), six to ten years (28.89%), 11-15 years (8.89%), and 15+ years (2.22%). Most nurses surveyed had been nurses for zero to ten years (82.22%), with one nurse (2.22%) for 26 to 30 years. The education level of the nurses surveyed included 24.44% with an Associate's Degree, 60% with a Bachelor's Degree, and 15.56% with a Master's Degree.

GLOBAID Pre-and Post-Test

Of the 45 participants, 31 nurses completed both the pre- and post-test (n=31), 40 nurses completed the pre-test only (n=40), and 36 nurses completed the post-test only (n=36). The average frequency of correct responses on the GLOBAID increased from 46% to 95%, with 5% of responses being incorrect out of 100%. Chi-square analysis resulted in a statistically significant difference between the pre- and post-test correct responses ($p = <.001$) (Table M1). Of all the participants, the frequency of correct responses on the GLOBAID pre-test on picture category 1A (picture J) was 38%, the frequency of correct responses on picture category 1B (picture K) was 85%, the frequency of correct responses on category 2A (picture H) was 43%, and the frequency of correct responses on category 2B (picture I) was 20%. For the GLOBAID post-test all scores increased in the frequency of correct responses with category 1A (picture J) 94%, category 1B (picture K) 97%, category 2A (picture H) 97%, and category 2B (picture I) 94% (Table M2).

KNOW-IAD Pre-and Post-Test

Of the 45 participants, 31 nurses completed both the pre- and post-test (n=31), 40 nurses completed the pre-test only (n=40), and 36 nurses completed the post-test (n=36). The average frequency of correct responses on the KNOW-IAD increased from 69% to 89% out of a possible 100% with 11% of responses being incorrect. Chi-square analysis resulted in a statistically

significant difference between pre- and post-test correct responses ($p = <.001$) (Table M3). The questions that had the lowest frequency of correct response on the pre-test in the etiology/risk domain was question three (28%), in the prevention/management domain question six (20%), question 13 (65%), question 16 (48%), and in the classification/diagnosis domain question nine (15%), question 14 (55%), and question 15 (63%) The questions with the highest correct responses on the pre-test included were all in the etiology/risk domain and included question one (98%), question four (100%), and question five (95%). On the KNOW-IAD post-test, the questions with the lowest correct responses were question three (78%) in the etiology/risk domain and question six (53%) in the prevention/management domain. The highest correct answer responses on the post-test were in both the etiology/risk and prevention/management domain and were questions one, four, and 18 at 100% (Table M4).

Monthly and NDNQI Pressure Injury Data

The monthly HAPI and incontinence incidence for the PCU varied per month from 2020 to 2023 (Table N1). The retrospective data from 2020 to 2023 included only HAPIs that had an incontinent component and were in the location of the perineal area. Pressure injuries not located in the perineal area, without an incontinence component, or diabetic ulcers were excluded from the data collection. According to the c-chart, September 2020 to December 2021 the monthly HAPI incidence analysis showed special cause variation of 15 points hugging the center line, defined per health care rules for identifying special cause variation, however this was prior to implementation of this project (Figure N1) (Provost & Murray, 2011). The control limits were adjusted due to the special cause occurring over several months resulting in a new average of 0.68 HAPIs per month with an upper control limit of 3.2, a lower limit of zero, and a benchmark of one. Control limits were then frozen to identify any further special cause variations (Provost &

Murray, 2011). The project was implemented in October 2022 and five months of data post-implementation demonstrate common cause variation (Figure N1).

The prevalence study quarter HAPI rate on the PCU from 2020 quarter one through four was zero, 2021 quarter one through four zero, and 2022 quarter one through four also zero. Quarters two and three in 2020 were exempt from the prevalence study due to Coronavirus 2019 (COVID-19) restrictions (Table O1). After the implementation of the educational module, the NDNQI prevalence data in 2022 quarter four and 2023 quarter one had remained at zero (Figure O1).

Discussion

The aim of this DNP EBP project revolved around analyzing the effectiveness of an incontinence learning module to fill in gaps in knowledge regarding IAD to decrease pressure injuries. Chi-square results showed an overall statistically significant increase in nurse knowledge post education in the GLOBAID and KNOW-IAD scores. Control charts, specifically (*c*-charts), illustrate specific data over time to see if an implemented change to a process resulted in a sustained process improvement (Provost & Murray, 2011). For this project, *c*-charts were used to count the number HAPIs per month and the rate of HAPIs in the NDNQI prevalence study per quarter to assess if the IAD education added in causing a positive process change.

Nurse Knowledge

The GLOBAID categorization tool allows for there to be a clear image of the clinical manifestations of each category of IAD, allowing nurses to document and appropriately treat the patients skin condition. There was an improvement in the post-test scores on every question on the GLOBAID after the educational module, indicating an increase in nurse knowledge regarding incontinence categorization (Figure M1). The statistical analysis of the pre-and post-test showed that the average frequency of correct responses increased by 50% from 46% to 96% which is well above the 70% expected value. A *p*-value < .001 suggested a statistically significant outcome that the educational module advanced nurse knowledge regarding the appearance of each IAD category and their ability to categorize the skin breakdown (Table M1). Current practice and documentation for IAD does not offer different categories and therefore most nurses did not even know there were different stages of IAD. The nurses excelled in their ability to properly identify the different categories of IAD after the educational module.

Picture I, category 2B: Skin loss with clinical signs of infection, had the highest improvement in frequency of correct responses between the pre- and post-test scores at 74%, followed by picture J, category 1A: Persistent redness without clinical signs of infection, at 56%. Category 2B displays infection which can appear as white scaling of the skin, satellite lesions, yellow, brown, grey, or green color changes to the wound bed, slough, excessive exudate and purulent drainage, and a shiny appearance to the skin (Beeckman et al., 2018; Beeckman et al., 2022b; Ferreria et al., 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018; Van den Bussche et al., 2018). The description of this category is often mistaken as a HAPI and not a result of uncontrolled incontinence. The education module focused to enhance nurse awareness to comprehensively analyze all aspects leading to skin breakdown and not pressure alone.

Results also revealed that many nurses' mis-categorized category 1A with category 1B. The skin pictured in category 1A appears with severe erythema that is localized to the buttocks, perineum, sacrum, and gluteal cleft (Beeckman et al., 2018; Van den Bussche et al., 2018). Category 1B picture depicts diffuse erythema that is in the same areas of category 1A, but that has spread with satellite lesions to the trochanters (Beeckman et al., 2018; Van den Bussche et al., 2018). While picture J does appear with significant erythema, picture K exhibits satellite lesions that are indicative of the colonization of *Candida albicans*.

The warm, dark, and acidic environment that IAD creates is a perfect breeding ground for fungal skin infections which increases the propensity of inflammation, skin breakdown, and pain (Beeckman et al., 2018; Ferreria et al., 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018; Van den Bussche et al., 2018; Voegeli & Hillery, 2021). Upon further review of the pre- and post-test results, it was clear that the nurses associated the severity of the erythematous skin with infection, not taking in all aspects of the skin irritation and breakdown. The educational module was able to address the

differences between category 1A and 1B with a focus on the presentation of IAD infection with satellite lesions. GLOBAID tool provided insight that there was a lack of knowledge regarding the appearance of IAD progression and infection. The improvement in post-test scores indicate that the educational module filled in the gap of confusion between persistent redness with or without clinical signs of infection.

Category 2A is usually mistaken for a stage 2 pressure injury as there is loss of skin, but the erosion is due to moisture and not pressure (Table M2) (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018b; Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022b; Coyer et al., 2017; Gray & Giuliano, 2018; Gray et al., 2022; Koloms et al., 2022). The pre-test scores indicated a gap in knowledge regarding how to categorize skin loss due to moisture and not pressure. It is important that nurses understand moisture erosion to decrease the misdiagnosis of HAPIs, enhance patient care, and decrease the cost to the organization (del Cotillo-Fuente et al., 2021; Gray & Giuliano, 2018; Koloms et al., 2022). After the educational module, the post-test scores suggested that the education provided enhanced nurse knowledge surrounding skin loss erosion from moisture and not pressure.

Most nurses are provided with focused education on pressure injuries and how to distinguish and treat each stage. There is also an area in the charting system for the nurse to chart on the pressure injury and the treatment provided. The results of this project revealed that there needs to be more education on IAD categorization and areas in the charting designated to chart the category of IAD and treatment regimen given to the patient. While the GLOBAID categorization tool exists, many charting systems still need to include it in their approach. The charting system only allows nurses to identify if the patient is incontinent but does not prompt the nurse to correctly categorize IAD or give the protocol on how to manage the incontinence.

Each category has unique characteristics and have different treatment and management strategies depending on the category.

Overall, the post-test scores of each category showed improvement indicating that there was an overall positive correlation between the educational module and nurse knowledge regarding the ability to distinguish and categorize IAD. The significant increase in test scores indicated that education on the different categories enhanced nurse knowledge with easy comprehension and applicability. It confirmed prior research that IAD categorization takes understanding and practice, just like with pressure injuries (Aquino et al., 2019; Rodríguez-Palma et al., 2021; Smith et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021). Once the charting has been approved with testing on the pilot unit, there will be an in-service on IAD and how to incorporate the new knowledge into the charting. There will also be an electronic module that the staff will be required to complete to show competence on IAD and the new charting system. After the pilot unit completes this new IAD protocol, it will be expanded to all unit's hospital wide.

The KNOW-IAD measures nurse knowledge regarding IAD etiology/risk, prevention/management, and classification/diagnosis and allows for the identification of knowledge gaps regarding incontinence. The average frequency of correct responses on the KNOW-IAD pre-and post-test increased by 20% from 69% to 89% which is above the expected value of 79%. A p -value $< .001$ suggested a statistically significant outcome that the education increased nurse knowledge regarding incontinence (Table M3).

The KNOW-IAD post-test indicated a significant increase in percentage scores in the prevention/management domain, indicating that most nurses enhanced their understanding regarding EBP treatment for IAD (Table M4). However, a question in this domain also had the lowest frequency of correct responses on the post-test, question six at 53%. The question

revolved around if a thick application layer of zinc ointment and a pad reduced the risk of IAD. While the use of zinc on IAD does enhance healing, the application of a thick layer, has been shown to decrease the ability of the absorbent pad to wick away incontinence moisture and enhances IAD (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018b; Beeckman, 2017; Coyer et al., 2020; de Cortillo-Fuente et al., 2021; Ferreria et al., 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018; Voegeli & Hillery, 2021; Zhang et al., 2021). Question three had a post-test score of 78% and while it is in the etiology/risk domain does raise the inquiry about the use of soap, water, and washcloths aiding in decreasing the risk for IAD development.

Soap products interfere with the normal pH of the skin, altering its natural flora, causing the skin to break down or become infected at a higher rate and the use of a washcloths increases physical trauma with friction, irritation, pain, and dries out the skin (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018b; Beeckman, 2017; de Cortillo-Fuente et al., 2021; Ferreria et al., 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021). Soap, water, and washcloths with the application of a thick layer of zinc paste are a staple for cleaning patients who are incontinent, however this practice is outdated and not supported by evidence. Nurses in the healthcare system come to the profession with varying educational backgrounds, attitudes, and traditions that can inhibit their ability to incorporate updated EBP changes into their daily routines regarding incontinent care (Abrams et al., 2018; Qiang et al., 2020; Zhang et al., 2021). Many nurses tend to maintain status quo and do not stay updated with EBP when treating incontinence. The advancement in evidence and the development of products have allowed for the enhancement of patient care treatments. It seems likely to conclude that nurses still need education on the expectations and reason for the use of evidence-based products on the skin that is why this question while showed improvement, still scored unsatisfactory for quality care practices.

While the results sparked growth in knowledge and understanding regarding IAD, the hospital must further educate the nurses on providing evidence-based incontinence treatment. While this project suggested that the nurses understand the etiology of IAD by scoring the highest in this domain, it is essential to enhance education on how to prevent, recognize, and treat IAD (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022b). Providing nurses with sufficient education to grasp these topics will aid in communicating why old practices cause more harm to the skin, the benefits of EBP in reducing IAD and HAPIs, and how new approaches enhance daily patient care (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022b; del-Cotillo-Fuente, 2020; Smith et al., 2018; Zhang et al., 2021). While there is significant research regarding IAD, it is imperative that the guidelines for EBP are translated into practice to ensure nurses are consistently using new evidence in their practice (Abrams et al., 2018).

The next group of missed questions, nine, 14, and 15, were from the category of classification/diagnosis. Question 14 increased in percentage on the pre-test to the post-test from 55% to 83%. The question asks how long treatment should be in place to identify IAD versus a HAPI correctly. It is important to properly identifying a HAPI for accountability and transparency however, when incontinence is involved, it does take a few days of observation and proper treatment to distinguish between IAD and HAPI (Banharak et al., 2021; Beeckman, 2017; Koloms et al., 2022; Stehlow et al., 2018; Van Damme et al., 2018). The results indicate that the CWOCN will need to educate staff on properly treating incontinence to allow the appropriate treatment to be effective instead of quickly giving a HAPI diagnosis (Table M4).

Question nine increased in frequency of correct responses on the pre-test to the post-test from 15% to 92%, as well as question 15 going from 63% to 94%. These questions revolved

around correctly identifying a category of IAD indicating that the educational module and the GLOBAID enhanced the knowledge of the different IAD categories (Table M4).

Lastly, question 12 had a decrease in the frequency of correct responses comparing the pre-test to the post-test from 83% to 81%. Now while this is not a significant decrease it is worth looking into further. The question revolved around comparing IAD to a stage 2 pressure injury. As mentioned earlier, IAD is often misdiagnosed as a pressure injury, increasing hospital costs, and reported data. Many nurses confuse IAD with a stage 2 or 3 pressure injury (Koloms et al., 2022). However, the etiology of the wound is from incontinence damage and not pressure. While the GLOBAID results indicated that there was an increase in knowledge regarding identifying the different categories of IAD, the KNOW-IAD results indicate that nurses still need more education distinguishing severe IAD from pressure injuries. There will need to be changes in the current HAPI education to include the IAD education module. When the two topics are merged it gives the ability to compare IAD verses HAPIs concurrently to enhance knowledge distinguishing the cause, effect, and treatment for each type of wound (Table M4).

Hospital Acquired Pressure Injuries

The project *c*-chart results did not show special cause variation after the educational module as there was an inability to interpret causation due to not enough data points after project implementation to suggest a positive process change (Provost & Murray, 2011). The chart had 37 data points representing the monthly incidence of HAPIs on the PCU, with only five data points after the educational module (Table N1). It was discovered that from September 2020 to December 2021, before project implementation, there was a special cause variation per the healthcare rules with 15 points hugging the center line (Figure N1) (Provost & Murray, 2011). Due to the persistence of the special cause the upper limits and lower limits were revised to

reflect the new process and renewed effort to continue to improve HAPI development expectations.

After analysis of the special cause process change, it was concluded that this special cause was due to the extensive work of the CWOCN in response to the hike in HAPIs in 2020. There was an increase in education, resources, skin champions, and other adjustments made post the COVID-19 crisis. It is apparent, by the special cause variation, that the extra effort put forth made an impact as there was a statistically significant decrease in HAPIs. With time, the HAPI rate began to increase in 2022, and the variability of the data showed there were inconsistencies in the process baseline. A change in the process needed to be initiated to keep the HAPI average within the limits of zero to 3.2 per month. While hospital census stayed consistent, there was an increase in patients with incontinence and HAPIs with a moisture component possibly increasing the HAPI incidence rate due to a gap of knowledge regarding the proper management of incontinence (Figure N1).

Post implementation the number of monthly HAPI's in the PCU stayed below the upper limit of 3.2 and at or below the benchmark of one, with four out of the five months at zero. The five points after the education showed that there has been a change in the amount of HAPIs per month as these points are below the average of 0.68; however, more data is needed to analyze if this educational module will create a special cause related to HAPIs. The project-lead will need additional data to analyze the sustainability of the educational module to interpret causation. While it is not statistically significant at this point, all five data points are within the expectations which indicate the project is moving the unit into a direction of change to enhance quality healthcare. To sustain the low monthly HAPI rate it will be important to continue monthly IAD

education on the floor and during staff meetings to continue to inform the staff on how to identify, categorize, and treat IAD to decrease HAPI development (Figure N1).

The pressure injury data from the next two consecutive NDNQI prevalence studies remained at the organizations goal of zero and under the benchmark of one after the implementation of the educational module, even with 65.2% of patients being surveyed having incontinence (Table O1). The projects implementation supports that the focused education on identifying, preventing, and treating IAD enhanced nurse awareness and knowledge surrounding IAD to aid in decreasing HAPIs at the organization (Figure O1).

Limitations

While this project was the first step in granting change to the facility and improving patient outcomes regarding incontinence knowledge, various barriers prevented specific project goals. The project was limited in staff that took the pre-and post-test ($n=40, 36$). There are limitations on the generalizability of the project's results due to the small sample size and might not represent the population of all nurses. Another limitation of the project included the short implementation period. Educating nurses over an extended period might increase knowledge as many nurses will re-hear IAD education and gain new insight with each session. Other barriers that prevented the level of expected achievement included that not all staff participated, some only took the pre-test or the post-test, and there are not enough data points after the projects implementation to assess if the IAD education caused a change in practice. Also, the post-test was given close, anywhere from immediately to 12-hours, after the IAD educational module. Taking a post-test quickly after education may skew results and in future studies it would benefit from retesting the population after several weeks to assess if the change in scores was due to short term recall or was effective in producing long-term memory change (Moro et al., 2021). It

would be beneficial to repeat the post-test quarterly to see if there was an increase in knowledge over time.

Future Implications, Recommendations, and Sustainability

The wound care department and the hospital are responsible for educating nurses on the identification, treatment, and prevention of IAD. There must be a focused module on IAD in addition to pressure injury education. The education provided to the nurses increased their IAD knowledge with identification, development, prevention, and treatment. It also increased the understanding on how to properly manage IAD to decrease the misdiagnosis and development of HAPIs. The future implications of the project will be the opportunity to bring awareness to IAD and how lack of education on this topic will cause a lack of evidence-based care, allowing nurses to mistreat or undertreat the skin, leading to lower patient quality outcomes.

Moving forward, it will be suggested to include the categories into the documentation along with the pressure injury charting to improve adequate management of IAD (Abrams et al., 2018; Beekman et al., 2018; Hödl et al., 2019). The characteristics of each IAD category, as well as treatment options, will be embedded into the documentation system and charted on daily. The next step to improve IAD prevention/ management knowledge is to update the treatment protocol to include the proper way of treating each IAD category. The CWOCN will present in the staff meetings for each unit, taking a 15-minute time slot, with the goal of enhancing the understanding of why old practices are not beneficial, what the new expectations are, and how to find resources on the floor for assistance in treating IAD to prevent additional pain, discomfort for the patients, and HAPI development while at the same time supporting the nurses to provide EBP care. The education will then be spread to each unit with an in-service and educational

module on the floor and during staff meetings, so all units are aware of the new treatment IAD protocol.

Lastly, the CWOCN will round on each floor monthly, using teach-back and the IAD educational brochure to enhance awareness, understanding and comprehension (Abrams et al., 2018). Teach-back is an evidence-based method to educate and confirm comprehension of new material and intends to increase learners understanding of new information (Masror Roudsari et al., 2021; Scott et al., 2019). It revolves around the technique of asking the listener to repeat back in their own words what was communicated to them or what they learned (Masror Roudsari et al., 2021; Ryan-Madonna, et al., 2019). The teach-back method, as well as teach-back with feedback has been found to train and enhance training, promotes adherence to new treatment plans, aids in knowledge retention, and increase learning a new procedure quickly (Ryan-Madonna, et al., 2019; Sleiman et al., 2023). More efficient training will translate into improved patient care, satisfaction, patient quality of life, and adherence to EBP guidelines (Sleiman et al., 2023; Ryan-Madonna, et al., 2019).

Sustainability, or successful long-term change, is critical to any EBP initiative and must be analyzed with the results of this project. The results of this project were positive and increased nurse knowledge about IAD and decreased HAPIs, ensuring that the sustainability of IAD education is prioritized. There will need to be modifications within the current HAPI education module to include IAD as the results of this project indicated nurses still need assistance distinguishing IAD categories from pressure injuries. The CWOCN can also support staff with adherence to the new IAD expectation by staff monthly rounding on each unit specifically for IAD questions or concerns. A change in the charting system will also aid in reenforcing IAD knowledge. The ability to categorize IAD in the skin charting tab with a description of each

category's appearance is a recommendation that might enhance the daily routine of assessing and treating IAD properly.

Conclusion

Inadequate incontinence recognition and management can result in patient physical and emotional pain, prolonged hospitalizations, increased nurse workload, misdiagnosis, development, worsening of pressure injuries, and increased costs and legal responsibility for the hospital. The educational IAD module allowed for a way to mitigate the issue of lack of IAD education and HAPIs. The Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice framework was used for this project as a foundation of how to improve nurse and patient outcomes. The project included identifying a problem of an increase in HAPIs and a rise in incontinent patients, prioritizing the need to increase nurse knowledge regarding IAD to decrease HAPIs, involving stakeholders and forming a team on the PCU that were willing to aid in the project, reviewing the literature, conducting research by analyzing retrospective monthly and quarterly HAPI data with an incontinent component, piloting the project with a staff pre-test, followed by education and a post-test, compiling all data, performing statistical analysis of the results, beginning to hardwire change in the system, and disseminating results.

The educational module demonstrated an evidence-based approach to increasing knowledge of IAD to decrease pressure injuries in patients with a high risk of skin complications. The knowledge gained can reduce the effects of IAD and help prevent the misdiagnosis and development of HAPIs altogether. The module initially demonstrated an improvement and has continued to improve patient outcomes as the HAPI rate has continued to be lower months after education.

Moving forward, to maintain the positive change of this project, focus on continued education about IAD and introducing a new charting system to aid in a detailed view of the skin and treatment options would benefit the quality of care given to patients. The project will need to maintain managerial backing, staff support, regular audits, huddle education, collaborative work with other departments and units, discussions about charting, and accountability by the CWOCN to allow for sustainability in the project to benefit the patients, nurses, and the organization. There will need to be continued theoretical and clinical education provided to staff to continue to increase nurse knowledge regarding IAD to decrease HAPIs. Additional data will be collected monthly and quarterly to continue to observe if the IAD caused and change in practice and patient outcomes. With more data points collected, the goal is the appearance of special cause variation indicating the IAD education caused a change in the current process and benefited the patients, nurses, and organization in reducing HAPIs.

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APPENDIX A

Iowa Model of Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Quality Care Practice

APPENDIX B

Permission Letter to use Iowa Model

From: Kimberly Jordan - University of Iowa Hospitals and Clinics survey-bounce@survey.uiowa.edu

Sent: Sunday, February 20, 2022 12:35:35 PM (UTC-08:00) Pacific Time (US & Canada)
To: Arellano, Emily emilyarellano@csu.fullerton.edu

Subject: Permission to Use The Iowa Model Revised: Evidence-Based Practice to Promote Excellence in Health Care

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Reference: Iowa Model Collaborative. (2017). Iowa model of evidence-based practice: Revisions and validation. *Worldviews on Evidence-Based Nursing*, 14(3), 175-182.
doi:10.1111/wvn.12223

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APPENDIX C

Literature Review Summary and Table of Evidence

Summary of Literature from Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature Database Search/EBSCO					
	Search Terms	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Incontinence associated dermatitis	Barriers	13	6	6	1
	Development AND Risk factor	18	4	8	6
	Prevalence	17	10	7	5
	Hospital-acquired pressure injury	7	2	2	3
AND	Length of stay	7	4	2	1
	Readmission	1	0	1	1
	Cost	6	3	3	2
	Knowledge	27	9	10	8

Note: Search limiters included peer-reviewed, full text, academic journals, English, publication date: 2017-2022, and Adult +65 or with no age filter.

Summary of Literature from PubMed

	Search Terms	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Incontinence associated dermatitis	Development	6	5	1	1
	Risk factors	9	8	1	1
	AND Length of stay	6	4	2	2

Note: Search limiters included peer-reviewed, full text, clinical trial, randomized control trial, English, publication date: 2017-2022.

Summary of Literature from Science Direct

	Search Terms	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Incontinence associated dermatitis	Barriers	36	30	6	1
	Development	43	36	7	2
	AND Prevalence	44	34	9	1

Note: Search limiters included peer-reviewed, research articles, English, publication date: 2017-2022, and nursing and health professions.

Prevalence of Incontinence Associated Dermatitis among Hospitalized Patients-Table of Evidence

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
Measure the prevalence of IAD and ITD upon admission and incidence of hospital acquired IAD and ITD in acutely ill adults (Arnold-Long & Johnson, 2019)	Descriptive, retrospective-cohort Observational (January 1, 2014-December 31, 2016) IDV: Proper identification of IAD/ITD DV: IAD/ITD prevalence CV: not a validated instrument to diagnose IAD/ITD, WOC expertise variation	Convenience sampling Urban community hospital in Charleston, South Carolina (n= 417) IC: Patients referred to WOC for evaluation and management of IAD/ITD EXC: All other patients	Secondary analysis of data collected for QI purpose gathered by WOC who identified IAD/ITD PR: existing IAD/ITD divided by the total number of patients admitted IR: diagnoses with IAD/ITD during their stay/the total number of patients admitted	IAD PR: 16% IAD IR:23% with age and BMI with significantly higher rates ($P=0.001, 0.03$) ITD PR:40% BMI significantly higher rates ($p=0.01$) ITD IR: 33%	Hospital-acquired IAD incidence was higher than prior studies based in acute settings Prevalence of ITD as higher than rates reported in prior studies Limitations: only reviewed charts referred to WOC, no use of validated tool, missed patients who were not WOC consulted, readmissions without IAD/ITD resolution.	Level III Moderate
ICU Patient prevalence rates of IAD and identification of IAD characteristics (Campbell et al., 2019)	Observational Prospective Longitudinal point prevalence survey (November 2015-November 2016) IDV: Proper use of IAD assessment tool	Convenience sampling 36-bed ICU, major metropolitan public hospital in Australia Total patient admission (n=351) Hospital-acquired IAD (n=59) Patients at risk for developing IAD (n=292)	APACHE II score Weekly SOFA, BSC, IAD severity categorization Tool, and process of care measures	Weekly IAD PR 0%-70% with 17% developing IAD Odds of IAD development significantly increased with age ($OR: 1.029, 95\% CI 1.005-1.054, p<0.001$), time in ICU ($OR 1.104, 95\% CI$	17% of patients developed IAD with rates varying from 0%-70%, with higher prevalence being linked to older age, diarrhea, BM volume, longer time in ICU, and respiratory or sepsis diagnoses Limitations: single hospital, single unit for low generalization, weekly assessment may have missed cases, did not record	Level III Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
	DV: Identification of IAD CV: age SOFA score, mechanical hours, BSC, APACHE II score, bowel movement volume, LOT in ICU	IC: at least 18 years old, admitted to ICU, skin with exposed urine, feces, or both EXC: admitted with pre-existing IAD, no skin exposure to feces, urine, or both, burns > 40% of body, or lifesaving treatment withdrawn/palliative care		1.063-1.146, $p < 0.001$), BSC score (OR: 4.363, 95% CI 2.091-9.106, $p < 0.013$), respiratory DX (OR: 3.657, 95% CI 1.399-9.563, $p = 0.008$), and sepsis DX (OR= 3.230, 95% CI 1.281-8.146, $p = 0.10$) Prevalence trend went from 10% to 24.1%	development of IAD following transfer to a general hospital unit	
INCT & IAD in acute care (Kayser et al., 2021)	Retrospective analysis (January 1, 2016-Decemebr 31, 2019) IDV: Proper identification of IAD DV: IAD prevalence CV: total cost, LOS, 30-day	Data retrieved from Premier Healthcare Database (n=235,141) IC: ≥ 18 YOA, admitted to hospital, had ICD-10-CM codes	Charlson Comorbidity index (CCI), APR-DRG scale	INCT prevalence 1.5% Prevalence IAD= 0.7% IAD ($p = 0.000$) to have APR-DRG major illness (31% vs 21%), higher CCI (2.4 vs 1.8), more immobile (5.5% vs 2.4%), cognitively impaired (21% vs 6.8%), less likely	IAD and IAD prevalence are lower than past research due to underreporting and lack of ICD-10-CM codes. Even with lower prevalence, still showed higher cost and worse outcomes for INCT patients and patients with IAD TX INCT= longer LOS, \uparrow re-admission rates, POA PI, HAPI, PI progress, higher cost of care	Level III Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
	readmission, sacral PI, HAPI, progression of HAPI			DC home (37% vs 64%). INCT = longer LOS (6.4 vs. 4.4), 1.4 times more likely to be readmitted, 4.7 times more likely to have a sacral admission, 5.1 times more likely to get a sacral HAPI, and 5.8 times more likely to have sacral PI progress to severe stage.	Need to regard INCT and IAD as a serious condition, need consistent assessment, prevention, treatment and management Limitations: Retrospective data difficult to find if IAD added in cost, use of ICD-10-CM codes may have excluded patients with IAD, risk of readmission and cost maybe underestimated, lack of benchmark data to compare	
IAD: Who is affected (Pather et al., 2021)	Prospective observational IDV: Proper identification of IAD DV: IAD prevalence CV: gender, age, comorbidities, diagnosis, types	Convenience sampling Major metropolitan hospital in Brisbane with 2 ICU (n=37) IC: ≥18 YOA with fecal INCT during admission to ICU EXC: ileostomy or colostomy, IAD on	APACHE III score, enteral feeding, continence status, type of linen or under pad, mobility status, medication, IAD severity categorization tool, Bristol stool form scale (BSFS)	IAD incidence= 35.1% IAD onset 3 days ± 2-4 IAD had 31% more movements, most had loose stool 92% of patients had mild category 1 IAD	Early identification of at risk patients and appropriate measures with standardized tools will have an impact on IAD. IAD rapid onset Early identification =early treatment=less severe IAD Limitations: small sample size, large number of variables, possible false positives	Level III Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
	of feed, Fecal/urine containment system, disposable fecal containment system and clean-up products, INCT and bowel variables, IAD characteristics, RX	admission, continent of urine and feces.				

Note: ICU=intensive care unit; IAD= incontinence associated dermatitis; IDV= independent variable; DV= defendant variable; CV= confounding variable; IC= inclusion criteria; EXC= exclusion criteria; SOFA= sequential organ failure assessment; BSC= bristol stool classification; APAHE II= acute physiology and chronic health evaluation II; PR= prevalence rate; OR= odds ratio; CI= confidence interval; BM= bowl movement; ITD= intertriginous dermatitis; WOC= wound, ostomy, continence; QI= quality improvement; PR= prevalence rate; IR: incidence rate; BMI= body mass index; BSFS= bristol stool form scale; INCT= incontinent; RX= medication; CCI= charlson comorbidity index; TX= treatment; DC= discharge; LOS= length of stay; HAPI= hospital acquired pressure injury/injuries; PI= pressure injury/injuries; POA= present on admission

Risk Factors for incontinence associated dermatitis- Table of Evidence

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
Prevalence and risk factors for the elderly for IAD (Ferreira et al., 2018)	Cross-sectional exploratory study (December 2015- July 2016)	Convenience sampling 2 public hospitals in the interior of the state of Sao Paulo	Instrument developed by researcher, ADL scale, Braden scale	IAD prevalence = 36.2% Combined INCT was the most prevalent, affecting 50%	The study found a high prevalence of IAD with incontinence. The early recognition of risk factors favors effective preventive actions.	Level IV Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
	IDV: Exposure to risk factors DV: IAD occurrence CVI: age, gender, BMI, type of INCT, type of effluent, dependency level, Braden score CVE: isolation, LOS, Feeding route, diuretic, laxative, sedation, diaper change frequency, outcome	(n=138) IC: M or F being ≥60 YOA, hospitalized for at least 24 hours, urinary and fecal INCT, consented EXC: indwelling catheter, urinary diversion or anuria, constipation, ostomy		IAD association: obesity (<i>OR</i> = 3.6 [1.2-10.4]), high level of dependence (<i>OR</i> = 2.4 [1.1-5.0]), very high risk to PI according to the Braden Scale [<i>OR</i> = 6.1 (1.4-26.9)] Risk factors: longer hospital stay (<i>OR</i> = 5.8 [2.6-12.9]), obesity (<i>OR</i> = 3.6 [1.2-10.4]), high level of dependence (<i>OR</i> = 2.4 [1.1-5.0]) and high risk for PI (<i>OR</i> = 6.1 [1.4-26.9])	IAD=↑ LOS > than 15 days, obese, very dependent, and at severe risk in the Braden Scale. Importance of investigation, attention to risk factors and actions focused on preventing this condition Limitations: not checking the pH of the soaps used, not preform direct exam to confirm candidiasis, absence of or incomplete records, no cognitive tool used, smaller sample size	
Independent risk factors for IAD development in patients with fecal INCT in ICU	Cross-sectional observational 8-month data collection	Convenience sampling (n=206) IC: ≥18 YOA, fecal INCT	APACHE II, Bristol stool chart, Glasgow coma scale, Braden scale, GLOBAID	Risk factors: liquid stool [<i>OR</i> 4.69; 95% <i>CI</i> 2.28-9.62], DM [<i>OR</i> 2.89; 95% <i>CI</i> 1.34-6.27], age [<i>OR</i> 1.05;	Liquid stool was strongest predictor of IAD Odd of developing IAD with liquid stool was almost 5x as high as in patients with loose or formed stool	Level IV Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
(Van Damme et al., 2018)	IDV: Exposure to risk factors DV: IAD category 2 CV: age, gender, LOS, smoking, APACHE II, mechanical ventilation, dialysis, infection, fever, tissue oxygenation, antibiotics, skin condition, malnutrition, DM, continence product use, skin care, urine INCT, loose or liquid stool, C- diff, mechanical chafing, low hemoglobin, nutritional support, diminished cognitive awareness	EXC: Patients with persistent redness due to incontinence (category 1) 48 ICU wards in 27 Belgian hospitals		95% CI 1.02- 1.08], smoking [OR 2.67; 95% CI 1.21-5.91], no use of diapers [OR 2.97; 95% CI 1.39-6.33], fever [OR 2.60; 95% CI 1.23- 5.53], low oxygen saturation [OR 2.15; 95% CI 1.03-4.48]	Liquid stool, DM, age, smoking, non-use of diapers, fever, and low oxygen saturation were independently associated with IAD category 2 Use of skin protocol is recommended targeting on prevention in high-risk patients Limitations: one point prevalence, missed patients, cross-section biases or incompleteness, did not look into RN knowledge and attitude or organization factors like staffing which could also be a risk factor	
Prevalence and risk factors of IAD using IPUPS	Retrospective analysis of 2016 IPUPS data 2016	Retrospective data from completed records that	Data from IPUPS	Prevalence of INCT patients that have IAD = 18%	IAD is a concern in facilities 20kg ↑ in weight was associated with a 7.1% ↑ in likelihood of IAD	Level III Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
(Kayser et al., 2019)	IDV: Risk factors for IAD DV: Prevalence of IAD CV: age, gender, weight, mobility status, and total Braden Scale for Predicting Pressure Sore Risk score	included the IAD question (n=13,615) IC: ≥18 YOA, hospitalized in acute care facility, long term care, resided in long term, and rehabilitation facilities in the US or Canada.		Prevalence of INCT & CONT patients that have IAD = 4.3% Prevalence of IAD in INCT patients = 18% (2406/13,615) Risk factors to ↑ IAD among INCT= fecal vs urinary (fecal (<i>OR</i> =1.61; <i>p</i> <0.001); fecal + urine (<i>OR</i> =1.55; <i>p</i> <0.001)), weight (<i>OR</i> =1.07; <i>P</i> <0.001), Braden scale score (<i>OR</i> =0.96; <i>p</i> <0.001), low mobility (<i>OR</i> =1.22; <i>p</i> <0.001), LOS (<i>OR</i> =1.11; <i>p</i> <0.001); additional linen layer	↑ Braden score by 3 points was associated with a 12% ↓ in the likelihood of IAD Each additional 5 days ↑ likelihood by 11% to get IAD Each additional layer of linen ↑ likelihood of IAD by 8.3% Need to standardize definitions of IAD and reporting guidelines Large range of variability of prevalence Provides further evidence that there is an association between IAD and PI as they share risk factors including reduced mobility, incontinence, additional linen layers, longer LOS, and Braden Score Limitations: IAD misdiagnosis, lacking accuracy of data, unknown start of IAD, sampling bias, model missing important risk factors	

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
				(<i>OR=1.08;</i> <i>p<0.001</i>)		
Incidence and risk factors for IAD in the ICU (Wang et al., 2018)	Prospective cohort (November 2016- Novemener 2017) IDV: Exposure to risk factors DV: IAD development CV: gender, consciousness, temperature, infection, antibiotic, immunosuppressor, sedative, mechanical ventilation, PAT score, Braden score, BMI, urinary INCT, fecal INCT, stool property, frequency of BM, double INCT	Convenience sampling Three Class 3, Grade A hospitals (comprising of 9 ICU) in Beijing (n=109) IC: urinary and/or fecal INCT, ≥18 YOA EXC: Existence of skin injuries, such as IAD, PI or skin avulsion, in the perineum or groin at admission, indwelling catheter and no leakage of urine or indwelling fecal-collection unit	Demographic and clinical data, Barthel index, Braden scale, NRS2002, and PAT	IAD incidence 23.9% IAD and non IAD saw differences with: Barthel index, Braden scale NRS2002, serum albumin, infection, fecal INCT, frequency, stool property, double INCT and PAT score (<i>p<0.05</i>) IAD protective factors: Braden score, serum albumin, and double INCT IAD risk factor: Double INCT (<i>OR = 10.512,</i> <i>95% CI 2.492-</i> <i>44.342, p <</i> <i>0.05</i>)	Higher morbidity if IAD present Low Braden = higher risk of IAD Higher serum albumin = lower risk of IAD The risk of IAD increased by 9.5 times with double INCT Prevention and nurse measures are required to maintain the skins integrity in the daily nursing practices to improve patient quality of life and quality of nurse care Need for training in clinical practices to differentiate between ID and PI, risk factors, and implementation of treatment Limitations: small sample, did not factor in improper care of skin as risk factor, some operation definitions were not included	Level II Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
Determining risk factors to develop a predicative model for IAD (Wei et al., 2019)	Prospective Quantitative study (October 2016-December 2017) IDV: Exposure to risk factors DV: IAD occurrence CV: age, gender, ICU type, LOS, PAT scores, bowel movement frequency, BSC, LOS, temp, DM, HTN, nutritional support, oxygen supply, coma, sedative, albumin level	Convenience sampling ICU at Tianjin Medical University General Hospital in China (n=266) IN: ≥18 YOA, without IAD or a PI at admission, fecal or urinary INCT, and using an indwelling catheter EXC: hospitalized <7 days, experience leaking of urine, unable to change positions 4 ICU, rehabilitation, gerontology units	PAT, Bristol stool scale, demographic and clinical variables	Incidence of IAD 65.4% Mean time was 3.95 ± 3.47 days Risk factors for IAD: Longer ICU LOS, HTN, enteral and parental nutrition, coma, sedative drugs, invasive oxygen supply, antibiotics, lower albumin levels, higher PAT score, more frequent bowel movements and loose stools (p<0.05)	The use of sedative drugs, coma status, PAT score, greater bowel movements frequency, and loose stools are independent risk factors to IAD Limitations: Single-centered cross-sectional study, small sample size, cleaning methods and products not assessed, other variables need to be analyzed	Level II Moderate

Note: IAD= incontinence associated dermatitis; IDV= independent variable; DV= defendant variable; CVI= confounding intrinsic variable; CVE= confounding extrinsic variable; IC= inclusion criteria; M= male; F= female; YOA= years of age; EXC= exclusion criteria; ADL= activity of daily living; OR= odds ratio; PI= pressure injury; LOS= length of stay; INCT= incontinent; ICU= intensive care unit; DV= defendant variable; APACHE II= acute physiology and chronic health evaluation II; DM= diabetes mellitus; CI=

confidence interval; RN= registered nurse; IPUPS= international pressure ulcer prevalence survey; US= united states; PI= pressure injury; BMI= body mass index; BM= bowel movement; PAT= perineal assessment tool; BSC= Bristol stool classification; HTN= hypertension

Incontinence Associated Dermatitis and Hospital Acquired Pressure Injuries- Table of Evidence

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
Measure the prevalence of INCT, IAD, & HAPI to determine associated practice gaps (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2018b)	Mixed Methods study (November 2015-January 2016) IDV: INCT, IAD, & PI identification and RN practice gaps DV: INCT, IAD, & PI prevalence	Convenience sampling 12 units in 4 hospitals (3 acute tertiary and 1 subacute) RN at time of audit was questioned IC: at least 18 years of age and admitted to units identified and RN caring for the patient at time of audit EXC: all other patients and nurses	Audit tool developed from literature review, patient observation, medical record review, and consultations with clinicians	INCT PR: 44.4% (n=111/250) IAD PR: 9.2% overall (n=23/250) IAD PR: 20.7% (n=23/111) HAPI PR: 3.6% (n=7/111) Association with IAD and HAPI ($P<0.05$) Association between INCT and limited mobility ($P<0.01$) Nurse response to gaps: 1- language used when discussing INCT pads 2- lack of/ varying INCT practices, management, knowledge, & IAD prevention	Associated between IAD and HAPI occurrences was significant INCT and mobility significantly related Lack of INCT practice puts patients at risk or secondary complications Limitations: High prevalence of HAPIs reported may affect overall prevalence. Lack of confounding variable analysis	Level III Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
Determine a difference in HAPI occurrence and IAD in INCT adults using disposable vs reusable under pads (Francis et al., 2017)	Randomized controlled trial IDV: Disposable (INT group) and reusable pads (CN group) DV: HAPI development with IAD	Cluster randomization of 4 units with similar patient acquitted and medical diagnosis in acute hospital in Brooklyn, New York Total (n=462) CN (n=252) INT (n=210) IC: All adults admitted to 4 units who were INCT on admission EXC: patients with 3 or more PIs located on the sacrum, buttocks, hips, or ischium on admission	Weekly data collection with NDNQI instrument for prevalence study	HAPIs significantly lower with disposable under pads (5% vs. 12% $P=0.02$) 14% of CN group with IAD developed HAPI and 0% with INT group	Use of disposable under pads reduced rates of HAPI in patients with IAD. Limitations: lower than suggested number of subjects, lack of randomization in IAD occurrences, lack of IAD severity identification to analyze improvements or deterioration of IAD	Level I High

Note: INCT= incontinent; IAD= incontinence associated dermatitis; HAPI= hospital acquired pressure injury/injuries; PI= pressure injury/injuries; RN= registered nurse; IDV= independent variable; DV= defendant variable; IC= inclusion criteria; EXC= exclusion criteria; PR= prevalence rate; INT= intervention; CN= control; NDNQI= national database for nurse quality indicators

Importance of Incontinence Associated Dermatitis Treatment- Table of Evidence

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
Before and after (InSPiRE) protocol to reduce IAD (Coyer et al., 2017)	RCT Quasi-experimental IDV: InSPiRE protocol DV: IAD DGV: gender, age, diagnosis, BMI, comorbidities, mode of admission, LOS in ICU, DC to ward or death CV: # of mechanical ventilation days, presence of indwelling catheter, type of fecal incontinence, vasopressor, and steroid meds	Convenience sampling 12-month timeframe in a 36-bed general adult ICU in Australian hospital Patients (n=146) CN: n=66 from April-August 2010 RN knowledge: September 2010 InSPiRE: n=80 October 2010—March 2011 IC: all patients admitted to ICU, ±18YOA, INCT (MECH VENT, sedated, and unable to control bowel function.), MECH VENT, in ICU>48 HRS. All patients had an indwelling catheter	Demographic and clinical data, Skin assessment tool, IAD severity tool, SOFA score, and IAD progress of care measures	1. IAD was lower in INT group (15%) compared to control (32%). ($p=0.016$). 2. InSPiRE lowered the # of IAD events over time ($p=0.022$). IAD developed at 9.4 days vs the control group at 7.4 days 3. IAD score was worse in InSPiRE ($p=0.017$) 4. Both groups had 98% of skin assessments and documentation complete	Use of a bundle EBP reduced incidence and delayed the development of IAD Prophylactic measures supported Ongoing assessment needed to avoid misdiagnosis and ensure appropriate targeted treatment regimens for IAD are in place Limitations: replication needed to confirm findings, weaker design (before and after) quasi-experimental where cofounders were not controlled, quantification of diarrhea not identified, no data collected on IAD outcomes like patient pain or RNs assessment.	Level II Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
		EXC: CA IAD on admission, IAD within 24 HRS of admission, and medical orders contradicting InSPiRE protocol				
Efficacy of IAD intervention on ICU patients (Coyer et al., 2020)	Open labeled pilot randomized controlled feasibility study (August 2017-March 2018) IDV: IAD TX protocol DV: IAD development	Randomization: study groups were assigned number General ICU in major public hospital in Queensland, Australia (n=31) (CN: n=16) (INT: n=15) IC: ±18 YOA in the ICU, INCT of urine or feces, and predicted ICU stay of 5 days EXC: admitted to the ICU with IAD, burns, fecal	Demographic and clinical variables, skin assessment, and presence of IAD and severity APACHE II, SOFA score, standardized physical examination tool for IAD, IAD severity categorization tool, enteral feeding and medication administration, bowel movement and frequency with type of fecal output, Bristol stool	Control: 17% developed IAD INT: 11% developed IAD Control: IAD score 3.5 (range 3-4) INT: IAD score 1.7(range, 1-3)	No significant findings between two groups, but IAD was reduced RN practice habits on the control IAD care vary per habit, misadministration, personal biases, and ease of use of product Clinician education is required to enhance understanding of a structured skin protocol for IAD Clinicians indicated reduced adherence to skin care guidelines with IAD treatment products Limitations: pilot trial, small sample size due to recruitment, trouble with staff adherence to study protocol	Level II Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
		containment device, PI, dermatologic DX, existing fungal infection, hypersensitivity to cyanoacrylate-based products	classification, process of care measures RN followed Control protocol = 58%-100% RN followed Protocol = 80%-100%			
Assess the impact of skin care bundle to reduce the incidence of MASD in ICU (del Cotillo-Fuente, Valls-Matarin, & Sandalinas-Mulero, 2021)	Quasi-experimental (June 2014-May 2018) IV: Online training and skin care program DV: Pre-and Post-comparison Variables: ICU LOS, BMI, INCT, fecal INCT, unable to communicate	Convenience sampling 12 bed ICU in a tertiary hospital in Barcelona, Spain First phase: pre-intervention (June 2014-April 2015) (n=145) Second phase-intervention Third phase-post-intervention (March 2017-March 2018) (n=145) IC: at least 18 years old, ICU admission for >48 HRS	Pre-and post-intervention: data collection, daily skin inspection, Braden scale, & GNEAUPP IAD categories Intervention-online training and skin care protocol	87.7% RN took online course IAD IR: Pre-intervention=29%; post-intervention=14.5%; (OR= 0.81; 95% CI 0.30-0.82) Onset of IAD: Pre-intervention=2 days; post-intervention=4days (P=0.005) IAD prevention measures: Pre-intervention=33.6%; post-intervention=81.3% (P<0.001)	RN online training and structured skin care reduced MASD by 50% Cleansing skin with non-irritating, products, restore skin barrier with emollients, and apply barrier to minimize exposure to moisture sources Limitations: data collection was only 14 days limited, number of nurses and facility	Level II Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
		EXC: admitted to the ICU with existing skin lesions in pelvic area, could not be handled due to medical contraindication, and DX with brain death				

Note: InSPiRE= interventional skin integrity protocol in a high risk environment; IAD= incontinence associated dermatitis; RCT= randomized control trial; IDV= independent variable; DV= defendant variable; DGV= demographic variables; CV= confounding variable; BMI= body mass index; LOS= length of stay; ICU=intensive care unit; DC= discharge; CN= control; RN= registered nurse; IC= inclusion criteria; EXC= exclusion criteria; INCT= incontinent; MECH VENT= mechanically ventilated; HRS= hours; CA= community acquired; SOFA= sequential organ failure assessment; INT= intervention; EBP= evidence based practice; YOA= years of age; DX= diagnosis; APACHE II= acute physiology and chronic health evaluation II; PI= pressure injury/injuries; MASD= moisture associated skin damage; BMI= body mass index; IR= incidence rate

Nurse Knowledge and Incontinence Associated Dermatitis- Table of Evidence

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
RN knowledge of IAD (Barakat-Johnson et al., 2022b)	Multicenter cross-sectional survey (November 2019-January 2020) IDV: IAD	Purposive 6 public hospitals in 5 health districts across New South Wales, Australia	Know-IAD 70% = correct satisfactory Demographic: profession, YOE, and clinical area	Mean scores on classification and diagnosis <50% Mean scores etiology and risk >50 % Role is associated with prevention and	Clinicians' low knowledge on classification, diagnosis, prevention, and management of IAD; higher knowledge on cause and risk factors of IAD Identified knowledge gaps for further education to improve assessment, prevention, and management of IAD	Level VI Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
	DV: IAD knowledge CV: ward type, role, YOE	18 wards participated: subacute and rehabilitation medicine, intensive care, general medical, acute geriatrics, and mixed surgical and palliative care (n=412) IC: RN, enrolled RN, undergraduate student RN, MD, allied health, and allied health students EXC: assistant to nursing		management (p=0.000) Entire set of items= 31.3%, Etiology & risk= 84.5%, Diag.=16.3%, PREV and Manage= 20.4%	Limitations: first study to report multidisciplinary group of IAD knowledge, cross-sectional design, limited data on demographics which may reduce confounding factors	
RN survey about IAD knowledge (Şahin et al., 2019)	Descriptive (July 2016-September 2016) IDV: IAD DV: IAD knowledge	Purposive 6 ICUs in academic research hospital in Ankara, Turkey (n=126)	Data collection form for determining the IAD knowledge levels of nurses was used that was designed by the researchers (59 items and 5	The mean knowledge score was 33.05 ± 10.16 (max-59) Low knowledge in most of the 5 sections Knowledge levels were higher among	Low knowledge levels overall, with higher levels of education performing better than lower levels All RN took care of IAD with no further training programs after schooling	Level VI Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
		IC: All LPN and RN ICU, Bachelor of science degree, employee, full-time	sections 1- skin structure & function, 2- definition & etiology of IAD, 3- IAD definition, 4- classification & evaluation, 5- prevention & TX)	nurses with a masters and lower among the LPN	RN need to identify, and timely treat IAD, distinguish from PI, understand assessment, hygiene, and treatment for IAD prevention and enhance patient care, clinical outcomes, and quality of life Limitations: one hospital of ICU RNs limiting generalizability, survey not undergone psychometric evaluation thus validity and reliability not known.	
Experience and training needs of ICU RNs on IAD (Zhang et al, 2021)	Descriptive qualitative (June 5, 2018- June 22, 1028) IDV: IAD DV: IAD knowledge	Purposive Respiratory RN from ICU in a general tertiary hospital in Beijing (n=10) IC: licensed RN, over 6 months experience, spoke Chinese, had experience with IAD	Open ended semi-structured questions and in-depth inquires based on answers	RN and IAD 4 themes 1) Nursing based on experience knowledge 2) Seeking self-improvement 3) Disunity of cleaning methods and wiping skills 4) Postponement of nursing	Themes of RN caring for IAD: relying on experience, seeking self-improvement, irregular treatment, and delaying nursing. Main obstacle: lack of knowledge, awareness, and supplies Training and management efforts should include: preventative education, supplies, training, diversifying training, and involve technology	Level VI Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
		EXC: RN on vacation, RN receiving refresher study and practice		care because of knowledge and awareness, and medical supplies	GOALS of training and management: establish an IAD prevention RN procedures, providing IAD care products, enhancing training content, diversifying methods, information system to assist RNs Limitations: single ICU limiting generalizability, need to look into quantitative measures	
ICU RN knowledge, attitude, and behavior of IAD (Qiang et al., 2020)	Descriptive (September 2019-October 2019) IDV: develop IAD standard prevention procedures, IAD incidence was monitored and analyzed, pay attention to IAD on a daily basis DV: Score of IAD behavior CV: gender, age, YOE, hierarchy,	Convenience sampling Secondary and tertiary hospitals in Guangdong province, China (n=500) IC: clinical RN, >1 year experience, volunteered EXC: RN experts involved in the design of	Questionnaire designed by the researchers 3 parts: knowledge (11 items), attitude (7 items), behavior (15 items) for a total of 33 items Demographic data collected	RN knowledge: 0-11 (7.23 ± 1.40) RN attitude: 7-28 (22.53±3.21) RN behavior: 27-59 (43.27±5.20) RN working 4-10 YRS ↑ knowledge vs 1-3 YRS ($p<0.005$) RN understanding: pathogenesis, result, and 2ndary stressors, correct skin care is low RN job categories and last EDU showed	Showed a difference between attitude and practice ICU RN knowledge on management and prevention needs to be improved, lack of systematic on the job IAD education and training including flipped classroom ICU RN have a good attitude and practical behaviors Promote and proactive theoretical and clinical education and IAD and ensure the RN know pathophysiology, risk factors, and prevention and treatment strategies for IAD	Level VI Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
	hospital grade, position, title, EDU level, last study time	the study questionnaire, RN currently undertaking education, training or study, and RN on leave		<p>significant difference ($p < 0.05$)</p> <p>RNs need to pay closer attention to IAD in their daily practice and should develop/adhere to IAD standard prevention procedure</p> <p>Establishment of IAD standard process, monitoring and analyzing IAD incidence, and daily attention to IAD were influencing factors of ICU RN score ($p < 0.001$)</p> <p>Monitoring and analyzing the incidence of IAD influence ICU RN prevention behaviors</p>	<p>Effective standard prevention procedures to reduce IAD</p> <p>Limitations: questionnaire needs to be tested for reliability and validity, sample size is small, not all hospitals in the region and may not be reflective of all ICU RNs</p>	
RN self- reported knowledge of IAD in the hospitalized elderly population	Descriptive and qualitative exploratory (second semester of 2016)	Purposive Large hospital in the North side of the Rio Grande do Sul State	Semi-structured interview with open and closed questions 1) Admission of the elderly	1) RN need to assess, verify, treat and prevent IAD with proper skin care. Also pay attention to high risk patients	Self-reported knowledge regarding prevention diagnosis, and treatment of IAD in which writer created the basis of a protocol/flowchart	Level VI Moderate

Purpose (Authors, Year)	Design/Variables	Sample/Setting	Measures/Tools	Results	Conclusion/Limitations/Notes	Level of Evidence
(Strehlow et al., 2018)	<p>IC: RN manager or caregiver, being in professional practice over the period of data collection for more than 6 months</p> <p>EXC: on vacation, retired, less than 6 months experience</p>	<p>Hospital RN from: ER, clinical and surgical ICU, general and cardiological ICU</p> <p>(n=14)</p>	<p>and IAD prevention</p> <p>2) IAD diagnosis in the elderly</p> <p>3) IAD treatment</p>	<p>2) Need to know etiology of IAD; know difference between PI and IAD. Understanding effects of IAD: impaired mobility, treatment options</p> <p>3) Need to know TX. No TX leads to: 2nd infections, increase \$\$, and LOS; RN challenges: economic issues, lack of knowledge, lack of help, lack of time</p> <p>Flowchart developed to aid in standardization: risk identification, prevention early diagnosis, and treatment</p>	<p>RN know the risk factors and consider it easy to diagnose but they do not know the differences in categories, which makes it difficult to treat and use appropriate treatment</p> <p>Standardize treatment and use a care flowchart to every incontinent patient enhancing safety and the quality of care in the same attention for each patient, reducing LOS, and \$</p> <p>Difficulties: frequent changes, diminished personnel, and effective prevention and treatment</p> <p>RN need to enhance education on prevention and criteria for TX of IAD as it is not part of the normal training</p> <p>Limitations: questionnaire needs to be tested for reliability and validity, sample size is small,</p>	

Note: RN= registered nurse; IAD= incontinence associated dermatitis; YOE= years of experience; IDV= independent variable; DV= defendant variable; CV= confounding variable; IC= inclusion criteria; EXC= exclusion criteria; MD= medical doctor; ICU= intensive care unit; BSN= Bachelor of science degree; LPN= license practical nurse; PI= pressure injury/injuries; EDU= education; TX= treatment; \$= cost

APPENDIX D

Letter of Authorization and Support

Institutional Approval Letter

05/3/2022

This letter is to show that, I, Candice Washilewski, as the Executive Director of Acute Care Nursing at Little Company of Mary Hospital Torrance, CA, give permission to Emily S Arellano, Dr. Laura Sarff, and Dr. Rachel McClanahan to conduct the project titled Enhancing Nurse Knowledge Regarding Incontinence to Prevent Hospital Acquired Pressure Injuries on the Progressive Care Unit.

Upon obtaining all necessary clearances from the Nurse Research Council and Clinical Scholarship at Little Company of Mary Hospital and after obtaining the necessary IRB determination/approval, the above-named project-lead is allow to:

- (1) collect data
- (2) access necessary documents/data via the data reported to NDNQI regarding HAPI occurrence
- (3) collect necessary documents/data via the NDNQI standardization collection tool
- (4) conduct necessary interactions with staff/patients relevant to their project
- (5) distribute KNOW-IAD and GLOBAID survey via pre- and post-test using the staff email and mid-shift huddles
- (6) provide evidence-based education to staff

The project-lead is responsible for ensuring that all activities related to conducting the project are in compliance with the policies that govern practice, HIPPA, and research and research-related regulations at Little Company of Mary Hospital and its covered entities. If you have any questions or concerns, please do not hesitate to contact me.

Signature:

Name: Candice Washilewski

Title: Executive Director of Acute Care Nursing

Signature:

Name: Maria Cindy Arce

Title: Wound Ostomy Continence Nurse

Signature:

Signature:

Name: Carmel Nicholls

Title: Executive Director of Critical Care

Signature:

Name: Lisa Bolash Lacy

Title: Interim Nurse Manager Progressive Care Unit

Signature:

Contact Information: 4101 Torrance Blvd.,
Torrance, CA 90503 (310) 303-5562

APPENDIX E**Institutional IRB Approval****PROJECT DETERMINATION**

Date: June 27, 2022

To: Cindy Arce, MSN, RN-C, CWCN, WCC, OMS
MariaCindyDia.Arce@providence.org
Emily Arellano MSN, RN-C, CWOCN, PHN
emilyarellano@csu.fullerton.edu

Cc: Lisa Bolash-Lacy BSN, RN
Lisa.Bolash-Lacy@providence.org
Laura Sarff, DNP, RN, MBA, CPHQ, NEA-BC
lasarff@fullerton.edu

From: Madeliene Carlos, CIM, CIP
Manager, Behavioral and Minimal Risk Panel

Project Title: “Enhancing Nurse Knowledge Regarding Incontinence to Prevent Hospital-Acquired Pressure Injuries”

This represents the IRB determination for the above referenced project.

The IRB has determined that this project, as submitted, does not meet the definition of human subjects’ research and does not require IRB review as defined in the federal regulations.

The determination is based upon the information submitted only, revisions must be submitted to the IRB prior to implementation.

The project may proceed as described in the documents submitted for review.

If you have questions related to this determination, please contact:

Madeliene Carlos, CIM, CIP | Manager, Behavioral and Minimal Risk Panel|
Madeliene.Carlos@providence.org

If you have questions related to QI/PI/EBP review, please contact us at:
PSJHIRBDetermination@providence.org

PROJECT DETERMINATION

Date: July 14, 2022

To: Cindy Arce, MSN, RN-C, CWCN, WCC, OMS
MariaCindyDia.Arce@providence.org

Emily Arellano MSN, RN-C, CWOCN, PHN
emilyarellano@csu.fullerton.edu

From: Madeliene Carlos, CIM, CIP
 Manager, Behavioral and Minimal Risk Panel

Project Title: “Enhancing Nurse Knowledge Regarding Incontinence to Prevent HospitalAcquired Pressure Injuries”

Thank you for submitting the modifications to your project.

Based upon the information submitted, the IRB’s determination remains the same.

(On June 27, 2022, the IRB has determined that this project, as submitted, does not meet the definition of human subjects’ research and does not require IRB review as defined in the federal regulations. The determination was based upon the information submitted only.)

The project may proceed as described in the document submitted for review.

This determination does not exempt you from following hospital policies and procedures as they relate to conduct of this project. It is your responsibility to ensure compliance with those policies.

APPENDIX F**Permission to use Ghent Global IAD Categorization Tool (GLOBAID)**

For valid consideration

This is to inform that the undersigned, professor dr. Dimitri Beeckman, hereby grants a permission to use the Ghent Global IAD Categorization Tool (GLOBIAD).

Prof. dr. Dimitri Beeckman

APPENDIX G**Permission to use Knowledge Instrument on Incontinence-Associated Dermatitis for Clinicians (KNOW-IAD)**

Sun 4/10/2022 4:16 AM

To: Arellano, Emily
From: Michelle Barakat-Johnson (Sydney LHD)
<Michelle.BarakatJohnson@health.nsw.gov.au>

Cc: Michelle Lai <michelle.lai@sydney.edu.au>

Hello Emily,

Nice to hear from you and thanks for reaching out.

Of course I give you permission to use the tool. Here is it attached. Feel free to adopt as well if you need to. Would you kindly acknowledge and cite the publication and would you send me a copy of the publication once finalised?

Many thanks
Michelle

Dr Michelle Barakat-Johnson

Clinical Lead and Nurse Manager Skin Integrity| **Sydney Local Health District**
HAC Pressure Injury Coordinator| **Sydney Local Health District**
Conjoint Associate Professor| **Faculty of Medicine and Health| University of Sydney**

Patient Safety and Quality Unit, Level 7
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The University of Sydney, Research Unit, Level 6, North Lifehouse (C39Z),Missenden Road
Camperdown 2050
Tel 02 86275184 T, F
michelle.barakatjohnson@health.nsw.gov.au

APPENDIX H

Informed Consent

Participant ID:

Birth month: _____

Mother's maiden name first initial: _____

Last digit of birth year: _____

Consent:

By checking this box, I agree to voluntarily participate in this DNP project, which includes taking a survey and listening to an education module. The survey will take 5-10 minutes with the education will take no greater than 5 minutes. Participation will be anonymous. Any questions regarding participation, the survey, or education please contact Emily Arellano 661-313-6115 or emilyarellano@csu.fullerton.edu.

“Emily Arellano and Cindy Arce will be conducting an evidence-based practice DNP project that will provide registered nurses with education regarding incontinence with the intent to enhance knowledge and decrease hospital acquired pressure injuries. The project will consist of a pre-post assessment which will be anonymous as well as a five minute educational session to discuss incontinence, secondary complications, and treatment recommendations. The two tools that will be used are the incontinence associated dermatitis knowledge tool (Know-IAD) which is an 18-item instrument that analyzes nurses' knowledge regarding the etiology and risk, classification of diagnosis, and prevention and management of IAD. The tool should take about 5 to 10 minutes to complete. The second tool is the GHENT global IAD tool (GLOBAID) which provides photos of different categories of IAD lesions and respondents are to identify the correct category of IAD. Even if you do not wish to participate, please still listen to the education session”

APPENDIX I

Demographic Survey

Demographic Information

Current Profession/Position Role

- RN
 RN- Charge
 RN- Relief charge
 RN- Administration
 RN- Other: _____

Educational Level

- Associates Degree (ADN)
 Bachelorette Degree (BSN)
 Masters Degree (MSN)
 Other: _____

Length of time as a Registered Nurse

- 0-5 years
 6-10 years
 11-15 years
 16-20 years
 21-25 years
 26-30 years
 30+ years

Current work area/unit name

- Progressive Care Unit (PCU)
 Other. Specify _____

Work shift

- AM (0700-1930)
 PM (1900-0730)

Length of time working in current work area/unit:

- 0-2 years
 3-5 years
 6-10 years
 11-15 years
 15+ years

Age

- 18-23 years
 24-29 years
 30-35 years
 36-42 years
 43-48 years
 49-54 years
 55-60 years
 60+ years

Gender

- Male
 Female
 Other: ____

APPENDIX J

Pre- and Post-Test

For each question, mark the box for True, False, or Don't Know.

Please read each question carefully and ensure that you answer each question. This survey takes approximately 5-10 minutes to complete.

Question	True	False	Don't Know
1. Incontinence-Associated Dermatitis (IAD) is skin damage associated with urine or feces affecting more than just the perineal area.			
2. IAD cannot be prevented if the patient suffers from sudden severe incontinence.			
3. Using water and soap to cleanse the skin after episodes of incontinence will reduce the skin pH and will lower the risk for IAD development.			
4. Risk factors for development of IAD are compromised mobility and inability to perform personal hygiene.			
5. IAD is a risk factor for the development of both superficial and deep pressure injuries.			
6. A thick application of zinc ointment applied with an absorbent incontinence pad will reduce the risk of IAD for incontinent patients.			
7. The incidence of IAD is generally less than 5% in patients in elderly care units.			
8. Hospitalized patients suffering from incontinence should have a systematic skin inspection performed every 48 hours.			
9. This picture can be classified as IAD category 1B - Persistent redness with clinical signs of infection. 			
10. Candidiasis (thrush) is one of the most common secondary infections associated with IAD.			

Question	True	False	Don't Know
11. In over 60% of clinical observations, IAD is mistakenly diagnosed as a pressure injury or vice versa.			
12. This picture depicts a pressure injury Category 2/Stage 2. 			
13. All-in-one large pads (nappy style) should be worn by all incontinent patients as part of IAD prevention even if the incontinence is infrequent.			
14. In some cases, IAD and pressure injury differentiation may not be possible until a management protocol has been in place for 3–5 days with response to treatment observed.			
15. This picture can be classified as IAD category 2A -Skin loss without clinical signs of infection. 			
16. Using soap and water with a washcloth is effective in preventing skin infections associated with IAD.			
17. Prevention of IAD should only be aimed at patients with frequent liquid stool.			
18. Management of IAD in this picture should comprise of: A skin cleanser, moisturizer, protectant/barrier and, in cases such as candidiasis (thrush), a microbiology sample to decide on other appropriate therapy.			

Note: Questions on published tool are in different order

Barakat-Johnson, M., Beeckman, D., Campbell, J., Dunk, A.-M., Lai, M., Stephenson, J., & Coyer, F. (2022). Development and psychometric testing of a knowledge instrument on incontinence-associated dermatitis for clinicians: The Know-IAD. *Journal of Wound, Ostomy, and Continence Nursing*, 49(1), 70–77.
<https://doi.org/10.1097/WON.0000000000000837>

Category	Description	Answer
1A	Persistent redness without clinical signs of infection	
1B	Persistent redness with clinical signs of infection	
2A	Skin loss without clinical signs of infection	
2B	Skin loss with clinical signs of infection	

Note: Categories on published tool are in order with definitions and descriptions

Beeckman, D., Van den Bussche, K., Alves, P., Arnold-Long, M., Beele, H., Ciprandi, G., Coyer, F., de Groot, T., De Meyer, D., Deschepper, E., Dunk, A., Fourie, A., García-Molina, P., Gray, M., Iblasi, A., Jelnes, R., Johansen, E., Karadağ, A., Leblanc, K., ... Kottner, J. (2018). Towards an international language for incontinence-associated dermatitis (IAD): Design and evaluation of psychometric properties of the ghent global IAD categorisation tool (GLOBIAD) in 30 countries. *British Journal of Dermatology*, 178(6), 1331-1340. <https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.16754>

Van den Bussche, K., Verhaeghe, S., Van Hecke, A., & Beeckman, D. (2018). The Ghent Global IAD Monitoring Tool (GLOBIAD-M) to monitor the healing of incontinence-associated dermatitis (IAD): Design and reliability study. *International Wound Journal*, 15(4), 555-564. <https://doi.org/10.1111/iwj.12898>

Thank you for your time.

APPENDIX K

Educational Brochure

<p>Southern California CSU DNP Consortium</p> <p>California State University, Fullerton California State University, Long Beach California State University, Los Angeles</p> <p>Enhancing Nurse Knowledge Regarding Incontinence to Prevent Hospital Acquired Pressure Injuries</p> <p>A DOCTORAL PROJECT</p> <p>Emily S. Arellano MSN, RN-C, BS, CWOCN, PHN Cindy Arce MSN, RN-C, CWCN, WCC, OMS</p>	<p>References</p> <p>Barakat-Johnson, M., Beekman, D., Campbell, J., Dunk, A. M., Lai, M., Stephenson, J., & Coyer, F. (2021). The development and psychometric testing of a knowledge tool on incontinence-associated dermatitis for clinicians (KnowIAD tool). <i>Journal of Wound Ostomy & Continence Nursing</i>, 49(1)70-77.</p> <p>Beekman, D., Van den Bussche, K., Alves, P., Arnold-Long, M., Beele, H., Ciprandi, G., Coyer, F., de Groot, T., De Meyer, D., Deschepper, E., Dunk, A., Fourie, A., Garcia-Molina, P., Gray, M., Iblasi, A., Jelnes, R., Johansen, E., Karadağ, A., Leblanc, K., ... Kottner, J. (2018). Towards an international language for incontinence-associated dermatitis (IAD): Design and evaluation of psychometric properties of the ghent global IAD categorisation tool (GLOBIAD) in 30 countries. <i>British Journal of Dermatology</i>, 178(6), 1331-1340. https://doi.org/10.1111/bjd.16754</p> <p>Permission to use tool & pictures granted by appropriate parties</p>	<p>What is Incontinence?</p> <p>The involuntary uncontrolled passage of urine/feces onto ANY area of the skin.</p> <p>What is Incontinence Associated Dermatitis (IAD)?</p> <p>Prolonged incontinence exposure leading to skin damage & can be prevented</p> <p>IAD FACTS:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Prevalence: 15%-95% ○ Risk Factors: Immobility & inability to perform personal hygiene ○ Secondary complications: Superficial and deep pressure injuries, Candidiasis infections, & increased RN workload
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Prevention of IAD:

- Manage ALL incontinence
- Inspect skin every 8 hours
- Monitor for sudden changes in bowels
- **NO** diapers or pads

Pressure Injuries:

- **Usually**, IAD is misdiagnosed as a pressure injury
- Differentiation may not be possible for 3-5 days with proper management

Cleaning & Management:

- **Do not use:** Soap and water. Will increase skin pH & risk for IAD
- **Must:** Cleanse, moisturize, and protect with barrier cream
- Use medicated wipes

GLOBAID Categorization**Category 1A (Early)**

Persistent **redness** without clinical signs of infection

Clinical Manifestations:

Intact skin, redness, irregular borders, shiny, macerated, painful

Category 1B (Mild)

Persistent **redness** with clinical signs of redness

Clinical Manifestations:

Intact skin with spreading redness, satellite lesions, irregular borders

Category 2A (Moderate)

Skin loss without clinical signs of infection

Clinical Manifestations:

Loss of skin, peeling, white scaling, redness, weeping, bleeding, small blisters

Category 2B (Severe)

Skin loss with clinical signs of infection

Clinical Manifestations:

Deep loss of skin, peeling, bleeding, satellite lesions, slough, purulent drainage

APPENDIX L

Demographic Survey Results

Demographics of Nurse Participants on Progressive Care Unit

Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
Nurse	<i>n</i> = 45	%
Current Profession/Position Role		
RN	35	77.78
RN-Charge	3	6.67
RN-Relief Charge	5	11.11
RN-Administration	2	4.44
Current Work Area/ Unit Name		
Progressive Care Unit (PCU)	43	95.56
Other	2	4.44
Age		
18-23 years	2	4.44
24-29 years	8	17.78
30-35 years	20	44.44
36-42 years	9	20.00
43-54 years	4	8.89
55-60 years	2	4.44
60+ years	0	0.00
Length of Time as a Registered Nurse		
0-5 years	19	42.22
6-10 years	18	40.00
11-15 years	4	8.89
16-20 years	2	4.44
21-25 years	1	2.22
26-30 years	1	2.22
30+ years	0	0
Length of Time Working in Current Work Area		

Demographics of Nurse Participants on Progressive Care Unit

Demographics	Frequency	Percentage
0-2 years	17	37.78
3-5 years	10	22.22
6-10 years	13	28.89
11-15 years	4	8.89
15+ years	1	2.22
Education Level		
Associate Degree (ADN)	11	24.44
Bachelorette Degree (BSN)	27	60.00
Master's Degree (MSN)	7	15.56
Current Work Shift		
AM (0700-1930)	28	62.22
PM (1900-0730)	17	37.78
Gender		
Male	6	13.33
Female	39	86.67

Note. Demographic data of nurses that participated in project implementation

APPENDIX M

Nurse Knowledge Results

Table M1

Observed and Expected Frequencies of GLOBAID Pre- and Post-Test

Frequency	GLOBAID		χ^2	df	p
	Correct	Incorrect			
Pre	46[71.00]	54[29.00]	60.71	1	< .001
Post	96[71.00]	4[29.00]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed/[Expected]. The results of the Chi-square test were significant based on an alpha value of .05, $\chi^2(1) = 60.71, p < .001$, suggesting that the frequency of correct responses and GLOBAID education are related to one another

Table M2

Frequency Table for GLOBAID Pre- and Post-Test

Question	Pre-Test <i>n=40</i>		Post-Test <i>n=36</i>	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Picture J - Category 1A	Persistent redness without clinical signs of infection			
Correct	15	38	34	94
Incorrect	25	63	2	6
Picture K - Category 1B	Persistent redness with clinical signs of infection			
Correct	34	85	35	97
Incorrect	6	15	1	3
Picture H - Category 2A	Skin loss without clinical signs of infection			
Correct	17	43	35	97
Incorrect	23	58	1	3
Picture I - Category 2B	Skin loss with clinical signs of infection			
Correct	8	20	34	94
Incorrect	32	80	2	6

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Table M3

Observed and Expected Frequencies of KNOW-IAD Pre- and Post-Test

Frequency	KNOW-IAD		χ^2	df	p
	Correct	Incorrect			
Pre	69[79.00]	31[21.00]	12.06	1	< .001
Post	89[79.00]	11[21.00]			

Note. Values formatted as Observed/[Expected]. The results of the Chi-square test were significant based on an alpha value of .05, $\chi^2(1) = 12.06$, $p < .001$, suggesting that the frequency of correct responses and KNOW-IAD education are related to one another.

Table M4

Frequency Table for KNOW-IAD Pre- and Post-Test

Variables	Pre-Test		Post-Test	
	<i>n</i> = 40		<i>n</i> = 36	
	<i>n</i>	%	<i>n</i>	%
Question 1:	Incontinence-Associated Dermatitis (IAD) is skin damage associated with urine or feces affecting more than just the perineal area.			
Domain Answer	Etiology/Risk True			
Correct	39	98	35	97
Incorrect	1	3	1	3
Question 2:	IAD cannot be prevented if the patient suffers from sudden severe incontinence.			
Domain Answer	Etiology/Risk False			
Correct	28	70	35	97
Incorrect	12	30	1	3

Question 3:	Using water and soap to cleanse the skin after episodes of incontinence will reduce the skin pH and will lower the risk for IAD development.			
Domain Answer	Etiology/Risk False			
Correct	11	28	8	78
Incorrect	29	73	28	22
Question 4:	Risk factors for development of IAD are compromised mobility and inability to perform personal hygiene.			
Domain Answer	Etiology/Risk True			
Correct	40	100	36	100
Incorrect	0	0	0	0
Question 5:	IAD is a risk factor for the development of both superficial and deep pressure injuries.			
Domain Answer	Etiology/Risk True			
Correct	38	95	35	97
Incorrect	2	5	1	3
Question 6:	A thick application of zinc ointment applied with an absorbent incontinence pad will reduce the risk of IAD for incontinent patients.			
Domain Answer	Prevention/Management False			
Correct	8	20	19	53
Incorrect	32	80	17	47
Question 7:	The incidence of IAD is generally less than 5% in patients in elderlcare.			
Domain Answer	Etiology/Risk False			
Correct	34	85	34	94
Incorrect	6	15	2	6
Question 8:	Hospitalized patients experiencing incontinence should have asystematic skin inspection performed every 48 hours.			

Domain Answer	Prevention/Management False				
Correct		32	80	32	89
Incorrect		8	20	4	11
Question 9:	This picture can be classified as IAD category 1B - Persistent redness with clinical signs of infection.				
Domain Answer	Classification/Diagnosis False				
Correct		6	15	33	92
Incorrect		34	85	3	8
Question 10:	Candidiasis (thrush) is one of the most common secondary infections associated with IAD.				
Domain Answer	Etiology/Risk True				
Correct		28	70	34	94
Incorrect		12	30	2	6
Question 11:	In over 60% of clinical observations, IAD is mistakenly diagnosed as a pressure injury or vice versa.				
Domain Answer	Classification/Diagnosis True				
Correct		34	85	34	94
Incorrect		6	15	2	6
Question 12:	This picture depicts a pressure injury Category/Stage 2.				
Domain Answer	Classification/Diagnosis False				
Correct		33	83	26	81
Incorrect		7	18	10	28
Question 13:	All-in-one large pads (nappy style) should be worn by all incontinent patients as part of IAD prevention even if the incontinence is infrequent.				
Domain Answer	Prevention/Management False				

Correct		26	65	29	81
Incorrect		14	35	7	19
Question 14:	In some cases, IAD and pressure injury differentiation may not be possible until a management protocol has been in place for 3 to 5 days with response to treatment observed.				
Domain Answer	Classification/Diagnosis True				
Correct		22	55	30	83
Incorrect		15	45	6	17
Question 15:	The picture below can be classified as IAD category 2A -Skin loss without clinical signs of infection.				
Domain Answer	Classification/Diagnosis True				
Correct		25	63	34	94
Incorrect		15	38	2	6
Question 16:	Using soap and water with a washcloth is effective in preventing skin infections associated with IAD.				
Domain Answer	Prevention/Management False				
Correct		19	48	32	89
Incorrect		21	53	4	11
Question 17:	Prevention of IAD should only be aimed at patients with frequent liquid stool.				
Domain Answer	Prevention/Management False				
Correct		36	90	35	97
Incorrect		4	10	1	3
Question 18:	Management of IAD in this picture should comprise of: A skin cleanser, moisturizer, protectant/barrier and in cases such as candidiasis(thrush), a microbiology sample to decide on other appropriate therapy.				
Domain Answer	Prevention/Management True				

Correct	35	88	36	100
Incorrect	5	13	0	0

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

Figure M1

Comparassion of GLOBAID and KNOW-IAD Average Fequency of Correst Responses Pre- and Post-Test

Note. The GLOBAID frequency of correct responses increased from 46% to 96% post IAD educational module. The KNOW-IAD frequency of correct responses increased from 69% to 89% post IAD educational module. GLOBAID= Ghent global incontinence associated dermatitis monitoring tool; KNOW-IAD= knowledge instrument on incontinence-associated dermatitis for clinicians; PCU= progressive care unit; IAD= incontinence associated dermatitis.

APPENDIX N

Progressive Care Unit Monthly Hospital Acquired Pressure Injury Data

Table N1

Hospital Acquired Pressure Injuries per Month on Pilot Unit

Year	Month	Total HAPI	HAPI: Perineum & Incontinence
2019	December	0	0
2020	January	0	0
	February	1	1
	March	1	0
	April	5	2
	May	1	0
	June	3	3
	July	2	0
	August	2	2
	September	0	0
	October	2	1
	November	0	0
	December	1	1
2021	January	0	0
	February	0	0
	March	0	0
	April	0	0
	May	1	1
	June	0	0
	July	1	1
	August	0	0
	September	1	0
	October	0	0
	November	1	1
	December	1	0
2022	January	3	3
	February	0	0
	March	2	1
	April	1	1
	May	2	2

Table N1*Hospital Acquired Pressure Injuries per Month on Pilot Unit*

Year	Month	Total HAPI	HAPI: Perineum & Incontinence
	June	1	1
	July	1	1
	August	0	0
	September	4	3
	October	0	0
	November	0	0
	December	2	0
2023	January	3	1
	February	0	0

Note. The frequency of monthly HAPI's from 2000-2023. The HAPI incidence included needed to be in a location on or near the perineum and had an incontinent component. The educational module was initiated before October 2022. Four of the five months post-implementation the monthly HAPI incidence was zero indicating a positive correlation between the IAD education module and decreasing HAPIs. HAPI= hospital acquired pressure injuries

Figure N1

C-chart of Monthly Progressive Care Unit Hospital acquired Pressure Injuries

Note. The chart reflects the total number of HAPIs on the PCU per month reflecting the unit's current performance on HAPI development. Implementation of the IAD education took place October 2022. There is a benchmark set at 1.0 with a unit goal of 0. An acceptable range of HAPI according to the data ranges from the lower limit of 0 to the upper limit of 3.2. There is a special cause from September 2020-December 2021. PCU=progressive care unit; HAPI=hospital acquired pressure injury; UCL=upper control limit; CL=control limit.

APPENDIX O

NDNQI Quarterly Hospital Acquired Pressure Injury Data

Table O1

Incontinence Prevalence Study Data from NDNQI from 2020-2023

Year	Quarter	Patients Surveyed	Incontinent Patients	Percentage	HAPI Total
2020	1	34	21	62%	0
	2	EXEMPT	EXEMPT	EXEMPT	0
	3	EXEMPT	EXEMPT	EXEMPT	0
	4	18	10	56%	0
2021	1	16	7	44%	0
	2	26	17	65%	0
	3	25	15	60%	0
	4	26	15	58%	0
2022	1	24	17	71%	0
	2	31	27	87%	0
	3	24	18	75%	0
	4	22	14	64%	0
2023	1	18	11	61%	0

Note. Incontinence prevalence in patients who were included in the NDNQI prevalence study.

Quarter 2two and three on 2020 were excluded due to COVID-19. COVID-19= coronavirus

disease of 2019; NDNQI=national database of nurse quality indicators

Figure O1

C-chart of NDNQI prevalence study data from 2020-2023

Note. The chart reflects the NDNQI prevalence study data from quarter one 2020 through quarter one 2023 reflecting the PCUs current performance on HAPI development. Project implementation started October 2022. There is a benchmark set at 1.0 with a unit goal of 0. An acceptable range of HAPI according to the data ranges from the lower limit of 0 to the upper limit 0 to still be in range. Q= quarter; PCU=progressive care unit; HAPI=hospital acquired pressure injury; UCL=upper control limit; CL=control limit; NDNQI=national database of nurse quality indicators